

EUREKA

European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices

**D4.3 - FarmBook data repository and search engine with
code/installation documentation and a user guide**

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Date	Changes
23/08/22	Added new paragraph regarding installation at page 31 (The virtual machine...FarmBook repository)
23/08/22	Added Annex IV pages 75-81

TASK 4.3: “FarmBook Data Repository Development”

Summary

Task 4.3 (“FarmBook Data Repository Development”) has been mainly concerned with the technical work related to: (i) the FarmBook’s digital repository setup (i.e., the digital repository for housing the Knowledge Objects of the MA projects) based on the design work done in tasks 3.3 (“Open and FAIR Data Repository Design”) and 3.4 (“Data Pipeline Design”); and (ii) the platform’s search engine development. In addition, there have been activities, executed as part of the task’s work, which have related to the definition of the metadata for the characterisation (annotation) of Knowledge Objects, as well as the finalisation of the model of agriculture- and forestry-related subjects initially proposed in Deliverable 3.2. The batch ingestion of Knowledge Objects into the FarmBook’s digital repository has been based on the ETL pipeline designed in Task 3.4 and has also involved the process of having the Knowledge Objects annotated with the defined metadata. An upload form allowing for the single upload of Knowledge Objects has also been developed and made available. The technical task work has also focused upon data security aspects by considering and developing two distinct mechanisms for user authentication purposes. The results of T4.3 have been: (i) the metadata defined for the annotation of Knowledge Objects; (ii) the final (and deployed) version of the (agriculture/forestry) subject model; (iii) the digital repository with the Knowledge Objects stored in it; (iv) the platform’s search engine; and (v) the upload form enabling single Knowledge Object uploads.

Deliverable Number	Work Package
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Beneficiaries	Deliverable Co-Author(s)
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	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethics	

Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
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	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	
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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
ETL	Extract – Transform – Load
EURAKNOS	Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System
EUREKA	EUropEan Knowledge repository for best Agricultural practices
FAIR	Findable- Accessible – Interoperable - Reusable
KR	Knowledge Reservoir
MA	Multi-Actor
MAP	Multi-actor project
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organisation System
TN	Thematic Network
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
UX	User Experience

1 Introduction

The aim of this report is to document the work in **Task 4.3** (“FarmBook Data Repository Development”), under the lead of AUA, regarding the setup of the FarmBook’s repository and the search engine on top of it. This work has taken place in the wider context of **WP4** (“Build the FarmBook and optimize it with end users”) towards meeting one of the key objectives of the EUREKA project, namely “*Explore the dynamic sustainability of project outputs and the FarmBook through the implementation of an EU wide agricultural knowledge base connecting outputs of MA projects*”. The activities executed in **Task 4.3** have focused on: (i) the setup of the FarmBook’s digital repository and the development of the platform’s search engine based on technology solutions enhancing data security; (ii) the integration of data into the repository; and (iii) the testing and evaluation of the digital repository’s performance against various workload scenarios. The main task goal has been to “*build a data repository, importing from and connecting with data sources from MAPs and beyond*”. To achieve an efficient implementation of activities and utilise resources from partners with the expertise to contribute to the task, the above-mentioned task-related goal was analysed into the following more specific objectives:

- **Obj1:** Setup of the EUREKA FarmBook’s digital repository.
- **Obj2:** Development of the EUREKA FarmBook’s platform search engine.
- **Obj3:** Definition of the metadata for describing the data (i.e., the Knowledge Objects in the FarmBook’s digital repository).
- **Obj4:** Preparation of Knowledge Objects to integrate them into the FarmBook repository.
- **Obj5:** Integration of Knowledge Objects into the FarmBook repository.
- **Obj6:** Evaluation of the EUREKA FarmBook digital repository’s performance.

The work done towards fulfilling the above goal and objectives has been based on the input received from **other WPs and tasks**. The context of the work in **Task 4.3** is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 - The context of the work in Task 4.3

Task 4.3 has received input from **Task 3.3** (the non-functional requirements considered for the conceptual design of the repository), **Task 3.4** (the design of the ETL pipeline for the ingestion of Knowledge Objects into the repository), and **Task 4.1** (functional requirements for the platform system). The user needs that have been captured as part of the work in **Task 2.3** (“Conclusions and mapping ideal user journeys”) have been used as input to define the non-functional and functional requirements of the FarmBook platform’s system. The digital repository and search engine built in **Task 4.3** are the input that has been provided to **Task 4.4** (“FarmBook Platform Development”). The results of the evaluation of the MA projects’ FAIRness made available from **Task 3.2** (“Data quality evaluation”) have allowed to illustrate the contribution of the design and repository setup-related decisions made in EUREKA towards delivering a FAIR digital repository solution.

Apart from AUA that led the work in **Task 4.3**, LFG has been the other primary beneficiary involved in the task. Yet, the activities of the task-related work have been done with the contribution of a broader project partner group (namely: MU, IDELE, IFOAM EU, UGent, ARC, LAAS, 3 APTA, RAU, AKI, and ZLTO). Table 1 lists the partners that contributed to the task, the activities they were involved into, the contribution from their side, as well as the related task objectives.

Table 1. Partners involved in the activities of Task 4.3, their contribution, and associated task objectives

Partner	Involvement in activity	Contribution	Related objectives
AUA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setup of the FarmBook’s digital repository. • Integration of data into the digital repository. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical expertise related to the repository’s setup. • Contribution to the development of the upload form to enable single Knowledge Object upload. • Training of the annotation team. • Annotation of Knowledge Objects with metadata. • Development of the list of metadata and the digital form of the subject model. • Monitoring and evaluation of the annotation task. • Integration of Knowledge Objects into the repository based on the ETL pipeline described in the report of Deliverable 3.2. 	Obj1, Obj3, Obj4, Obj5
LFG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of the FarmBook platform’s search engine. • Testing and evaluation of the digital repository’s performance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical expertise related to the development of the search engine. • Testing and evaluation of the digital repository’s performance. • Contribution to the development of the subject model (by providing feedback). 	Obj2, Obj6
MU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setup of the FarmBook’s digital repository. • Integration of data into the digital repository. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical expertise related to the repository’s setup. • Development of the upload form to enable single Knowledge Object upload. 	Obj1, Obj3, Obj5

Partner	Involvement in activity	Contribution	Related objectives
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to the development of the set of metadata. • Contribution to the development of the subject model (by providing feedback). • Integration of Knowledge Objects into the repository based on the ETL pipeline described in the report of Deliverable 3.2. 	
IDELE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of data into the digital repository. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of the subject model. • Annotation of Knowledge Objects with metadata. 	Obj4
IFOAM EU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of data into the digital repository. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation and refinement of the subject model. • Annotation of Knowledge Objects with metadata. 	Obj4
AKI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of data into the digital repository. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to the development of the subject model (by providing feedback). • Annotation of Knowledge Objects with metadata. 	Obj4
ARC, LAAS, RAU, UGent, 3 APTA, ZLTO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of data into the digital repository. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annotation of Knowledge Objects with metadata. 	Obj4

Based on the above, the report is structured as follows: in Section 2 (“Methodology”) a brief overview of methodological aspects of the work in **Task 4.3** is given. Section 3 (“Conceptual design and FarmBook data repository technologies”) provides a discussion on the metadata used to annotate the Knowledge Objects in the repository, the refinement of the subject model (initially described in the report of **Deliverable 3.2**¹) and the creation of an elaborated version of it to be utilised for providing values to the metadata property related to the subject addressed in the Knowledge Object’s content, as well as the description of the technologies utilised for the repository’s set up. In Section 4 (“Ingestion of Knowledge Objects into the FarmBook data repository”), the focus is on the ingestion of Knowledge Objects into the FarmBook (from the training of the annotation team and the annotation process to the description of the ingestion/upload options available and the evaluation of the repository’s FAIRness). User authentication mechanisms that have been built for providing security affordances are presented in Section 5 (“User authentication”), whereas Section 6 (“Testing the FarmBook data repository”) outlines the results of the testing and evaluation of the repository’s performance under various workload scenarios. A guide of the FarmBook platform’s search engine is available in Section 7 (“Knowledge Object search capabilities and user guide”). Concluding remarks and final insights are provided in Section 8 (“Discussion and conclusions”).

¹ Panoutsopoulos, H. et al. (2021a). D3.2: Data Repository Design and Data Pipeline Design. EUREKA project.

2 Methodology

The work in **Task 4.3** has involved four (4) core activities, each of which has related to a step in the adopted methodology. These activities/methodology steps have been: (i) the setup of the FarmBook repository; (ii) the development of the FarmBook platform’s search engine; (iii) the integration of data into the digital repository; and (iv) the testing and evaluation of the performance of the digital repository. Figure 2 shows the steps of the methodology and their sequence.

Figure 2 - The methodology followed in Task 4.3

Part of the work involved in the “integration of data into the digital repository” has been the revision of the model of agriculture- and forestry-related subjects initially proposed in the report of **Deliverable 3.2**. The methodology adopted for this part of the work and the revision-related details are outlined in Section 3.2 (“The EUREKA model of agriculture- and forestry-related subjects”). This step has also involved: (i) the assembly and training of a team of annotators to annotate the Knowledge Objects aimed to be ingested in batches into the digital repository with metadata; (ii) the annotation of the Knowledge Objects; (iii) the ingestion of the Knowledge Objects into the FarmBook’s repository; and (iv) the development of a form to enable the upload of single Knowledge Objects by the users. The objectives of the task related to each step of the methodology and the involved partners are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2 - Steps in the methodology of Task 4.3, associated objectives, and project partners that have been involved

Methodology step	Associated objectives	Involved partners
Setup of the FarmBook digital repository	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obj1: Setup of the EUREKA FarmBook’s digital repository. 	AUA, MU
Development of the FarmBook platform’s search engine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obj2: Development of the EUREKA FarmBook’s platform search engine. 	LFG
Integration of data into the digital repository	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obj3: Definition of the metadata for describing the data (i.e., the Knowledge Objects in the EUREKA FarmBook’s digital repository). • Obj4: Preparation of data (i.e., Knowledge Objects) to integrate them into the EUREKA FarmBook repository. • Obj5: Integration of data (i.e., Knowledge Objects) into the FarmBook repository. 	AUA, MU, IDELE, IFOAM EU, AKI, ARC, LAAS, RAU, UGent, 3 APTA, ZLTO

Testing and evaluation of the performance of the digital repository	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obj6: Evaluation of the EUREKA FarmBook digital repository’s performance. 	LFG
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3 Conceptual design and FarmBook data repository technologies

3.1 The EUREKA FarmBook data model and the metadata used to annotate Knowledge Objects

One of the main goals of EUREKA has been to identify and select agriculture- and forestry-related outputs of EU-funded, H2020 MA projects (the so-called Knowledge Objects) containing data and information of importance and relevance to the rural and scientific community, to render them available and accessible via a standards-based, easily searchable, and open-source repository (i.e., the EU FarmBook). In this way, the longevity and better sharing of the digital dissemination/training material and research outputs of MA projects can be ensured, enhancing a wider cross-sectoral and long-term use of these materials to enable future developments by the EU AKISs. There are considerable challenges to address in this effort, mostly relating to the heterogeneity of the digital objects to be integrated into the digital repository. To this end, a semantic data model (the EUREKA FarmBook data model), shown in Figure 3 below, has been developed in an attempt to propose solutions, in the spirit of the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), towards homogenising the description and labelling of the various digital output and repository types, as well as the variety of designs, standards, and formats used to build them. The EUREKA FarmBook data model has provided the blueprint for the design and development of the FarmBook repository by enabling the definition of a minimum set of metadata (together with their value requirements) for the onboarding of the MA project Knowledge Objects into the FarmBook’s digital repository.

Figure 3 - The EUREKA FarmBook data model

The aim of the data model is to provide a structure able to formally describe the entities and relations of importance for the description of the Knowledge Objects, which in turn have been used to define the metadata for the Knowledge Objects’ annotation. Details about the requirements and specifications that guided the data model design, the steps followed to create it, as well as how it extends the relevant work in EURAKNOS², are available in Section 3.4 (“The FarmBook data model”) of the report of **Deliverable 3.2** (“Data Repository Design and Data Pipeline Design”).

The classes defined in the EUREKA FarmBook data model and the Knowledge Object-related information they convey are listed in Table 3 below.

Table 3 - The classes of the EUREKA FarmBook data model, their source ontologies/vocabularies, and information conveyed by them

Class	Source ontology/vocabulary	Information conveyed
frapo:Output	FRAPO ³	The Knowledge Object (i.e., the digital output of a MAP)
foaf:Project	FOAF ⁴	The MAP in which the Knowledge Object has been created.
dct:Agent	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative ⁵	The person(s) or organisation(s) involved in the creation of a MAP Knowledge Object.
schema:Place	Schema.org ⁶	The place (geographic location) associated with the content of the Knowledge Object.
ontopic:Subject	Ontopic ontology ⁷	The subject (topic) of a Knowledge Object (i.e., what the Knowledge Object is about).
schema:Dataset schema:TextDigitalDocument schema:PresentationDigitalDocument schema:AudioObject schema:ImageObject schema:VideoObject schema:SoftwareApplication	Schema.org	The different Knowledge Object Categories considered in the data model (i.e., datasets, documents, presentations/slideshows, audios, images, videos, and software apps).

The **relation types (object properties)** in the data model, their source ontologies, and the information conveyed by them are listed in Table 4 below.

² The data modelling-related work undertaken in EURAKNOS is reported in: Van Hal et al. (2020). D3.2: REPORT ON HIKR DESIGN - Report on database, technology choices & e-KRP recommendations. EURAKNOS project.

³ <http://www.sparontologies.net/ontologies/frapo>

⁴ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>

⁵ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

⁶ <https://schema.org/>

⁷ <http://www.ontologydesignpatterns.org/ont/dul/ontopic.owl>

Table 4 - The object properties (relation types) defined in the EUREKA FarmBook data model, their source ontologies/vocabularies, and information conveyed by them

Object property (relation type)	Source ontology/vocabulary	Information conveyed
frapo:isOutputOf	FRAPO	Relation between the digital output and the MAP it comes from.
dct:creator	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative	Relation between the digital output and the person(s) or the organisation(s) involved in their creation.
dct:subject	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative	Relation between the digital output and the subject(s)/ topic(s) addressed in it.
schema:contentLocation	Schema.org	Relation between the content of the MAP digital output and the geographic location the content of the output relates.
rdfs:subClassOf	RDF Schema ⁸	Hierarchical relations between classes of the data model.

The **datatype properties** defined in the EUREKA data model, their source ontologies/vocabularies, as well as the information conveyed by them are listed in Table 5 below.

Table 5 - The datatype properties defined in the EUREKA FarmBook data model, their source ontologies/controlled vocabularies, and the information conveyed by them

Datatype property	Source ontology/vocabulary	Information conveyed
dct:title	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative	Datatype property used to link a digital output to its title.
schema:description	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a digital output to a short textual description of its content.
schema:keywords	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a digital output to a list of relevant keywords.
schema:inLanguage	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a digital output to the language in which its content is available.
schema:dateCreated	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a digital output to the date of its creation.
schema:fileSize	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a digital output to the size of the digital file (e.g., in KBs or MBs) via which it becomes available.
schema:license	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a digital output to the license (for instance, a Creative Commons license) specifying the terms for reusing it.

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>

Datatype property	Source ontology/vocabulary	Information conveyed
dct:format	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative	Datatype property used to link a digital output to the format in which the respective digital file is available (e.g., .pdf, .ppt, .tiff).
dct:type	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative	Datatype property used to link a digital output to its type (e.g., practice abstract).
schema:potentialAction	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a digital output to the purpose it has been created for (e.g., to be used for education/training purposes).
schema:ratingValue	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a digital output to a quantitative assessment of its content made by users.
schema:comment	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a digital output to comments made on its content by users.
schema:name	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a MAP, person/organisation being involved in the creation of a Knowledge Object, or geographic location (associated with the content of a Knowledge Object) to its name.
schema:alternateName	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a MAP to its acronym.
schema:url	Schema.org	Datatype property used to link a digital output or MAP to its URL.

Based on the EUREKA FarmBook data model, the following set of metadata (see Table 6 below) has been defined for annotating the Knowledge Objects prior to their ingestion into the repository.

Table 6 - The set of metadata properties used for the annotation of the MAP Knowledge Objects (asterisk, '', indicates a required field).*

Metadata property name	Associated datatype property of the data model	Metadata property description
Title (*)	http://purl.org/dc/terms/title	The title of the MAP Knowledge Object.
Description (*)	https://schema.org/description	A short textual description of the MAP Knowledge Object.
Keywords (*)	https://schema.org/keywords	A list of keywords linked to the MAP Knowledge Object.
Creator(s) (*)	http://purl.org/dc/terms/creator	The person(s) or organisation(s) involved in the creation of the Knowledge Object.
Language(s) (*)	https://schema.org/inLanguage	The language(s) in which the content of the Knowledge Object is available.
Date of completion	https://schema.org/dateCreated	The date when the Knowledge Object's creation was completed.
Intended purpose (*)	https://schema.org/potentialAction	The purpose that the Knowledge Object was created for.

Metadata property name	Associated datatype property of the data model	Metadata property description
Geographic location(s)	https://schema.org/contentLocation	The geographic location(s) that the (content of the) Knowledge Object relates to.
Knowledge Object URL	https://schema.org/url	The Knowledge Object's URL.
Category (*)	-	The category that the Knowledge Object belongs to (i.e., dataset, document, image, presentation/ slideshow, audio, video, software application).
Type (*)	http://purl.org/dc/terms/type	The Knowledge Object's type.
Subject (Level 1) (*)	http://purl.org/dc/terms/subject	The main subject (topic) of the Knowledge Object.
Subject (Level 2) (*)	http://purl.org/dc/terms/subject	The subtopics associated with the (content of the) Knowledge Object.
License	https://schema.org/license	The license specifying the terms under which the Knowledge Object can be reused.
Format	http://purl.org/dc/terms/format	The format of the file via which the Knowledge Object becomes available.
File size	https://schema.org/fileSize	The size of the file (e.g., in KBs or MBs) via which the Knowledge Object becomes available.
Project name (*)	https://schema.org/name	The name of the MAP in which the Knowledge Object has been created.
Project acronym (*)	https://schema.org/alternateName	The acronym of the MAP in which the Knowledge Object has been created.
Project URL (*)	https://schema.org/url	The URL (of the official website) of the Knowledge Object's source MAP.

The asterisk (*) is used to indicate that a category is mandatory. These include “category”, “language(s)”, “geographic location(s)”, “type”, “intended purpose”, and “subject” (Level 1 and 2). The lists of predefined values for these properties are available in Annex I (“Lists of predefined EUREKA metadata values”).

3.2 The EUREKA model of agriculture- and forestry-related subjects

The aim of this section is to elaborate on the work related to the development of a model describing the subjects/topics addressed by the Knowledge Objects in the EUREKA FarmBook's repository (initial result reported in **Deliverable 3.2**⁹). In Deliverable 3.2 the results of a preliminary modelling attempt have been presented together with the system requirements associated with this effort. The initially proposed model (built based on the SKOS recommendation¹⁰) consisted of a set of concepts and their semantic relations.

⁹ Panoutsopoulos, H. et al. (2021a). D3.2: Data Repository Design and Data Pipeline Design. EUREKA project.

¹⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/>

Starting from a broad categorisation of the agricultural sectors proposed by EIP-AGRI¹¹ (namely, “arable and horticultural crops”, “perennial crops”, “forestry”, “livestock and dairy”, and “agri-food industry”) and the top-level topic categories proposed in EURAKNOS (namely, “crop farming”, “livestock”, “forestry”, “environment”, “climate”, and “socio-economic context”), the core idea behind the creation of the initial version of the model was to re-use concepts from existing ontologies and vocabularies in order to formally describe the subjects and towards addressing the findability and interoperability dimensions of the FAIR principles. Details on the initial version of the subject model and its creation are available in **Deliverable 3.2**, Section 3.5 (“A preliminary model of the subjects addressed in the FarmBook knowledge objects”).

To better map the heterogeneity of the subjects/topics addressed in the dissemination material of the various MA projects, as well as the need of the agriculture and forestry community to efficiently search for and find digital content of relevance and importance, the initial model creation process underwent a revision process. The revision involved the re-use of the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy of agricultural subjects/topics (i.e., the EIP-AGRI’s “macro-categories” used to tag the content available from its database¹²) and not just its categorisation of agricultural sectors (considered for the first version of the model). The reason for such a decision has been the extensive use of the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy by the agriculture and forestry community and therefore its familiarity with it. By considering the EIP-AGRI’s topic categories as the core concepts in the model, another aspect of the revision process related to the association of each taxonomy topics with a set of AGROVOC concepts of a broader, narrower, and similar scope, as the means to provide enhanced search results. The steps of the process to revise the model of agriculture- and forestry-related subjects are shown in Figure 4 below. The model revision and finalisation process initiated in the beginning of the summer of 2021 and ended close to the end of December 2021.

Figure 4 - The steps followed to revise the initial version of the EUREKA FarmBook’s model of agriculture- and forestry-related topics to create the final version

The work involved in each step of the methodology is described below.

Assignment of roles and responsibilities

The revision of the already existing version of the model to formally describe the agriculture- and forestry-related subjects addressed by the Knowledge Objects housed in the digital repository, and its finalisation, has been a task requiring various kinds of expertise brought by several partner organisations. The EUREKA partners involved in this process were: AUA, MU, IDELE, IFOAM EU, UGent, AKI, and LFG. The contribution of each partner is highlighted in Table 7 below.

¹¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/about>

¹² https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects?search_api_views_fulltext=&field_project_funding_source_list=4

Table 7 - Description of the contribution of EUREKA project partners in the process of the EUREKA FarmBook's subject model revision and finalisation

Partner organisation	Contribution	Methodology step
AUA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By bringing in expertise related to conceptual modelling, semantic web technologies and standards, and data FAIRness AUA contributed to the establishment of semantic associations between the EIP-AGRI's topic categories and the AGROVOC concepts. By being the organisation in lead of Task 4.3, AUA had the overall responsibility of the work, monitored the process implementation, and provided support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of a semantic network for each topic in the EIP-AGRI's taxonomy Assembly of the EUREKA FarmBook's subject model
MU	By bringing in expertise related to conceptual modelling, semantic web technologies and standards, and data FAIRness MU contributed to the establishment of semantic associations between the EIP-AGRI's topic categories and the AGROVOC concepts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of a semantic network for each topic in the EIP-AGRI's taxonomy Assembly of the EUREKA FarmBook's subject model
IDELE	By providing domain expertise, IDELE was involved in the part of the work relating to the core part of the topic model revision process, namely the identification (and establishment) of associations between the topic categories of the EIP-AGRI's taxonomy and AGROVOC concepts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of the EIP-AGRI's taxonomy of agricultural topics Creation of links between the EIP-AGRI topics and the AGROVOC concepts
IFOAM EU	By providing domain expertise, IFOAM EU was involved in the evaluation and fine tuning of the final version of the EUREKA FarmBook's model of agriculture- and forestry-related subjects.	Evaluation of the EUREKA FarmBook's subject model
UGent	By being the coordinator of the project and given the importance of the specific effort, UGent contributed to the monitoring of the process and the provision of support.	All methodology steps (support throughout the process).
AKI	By bringing in domain expertise, AKI provided feedback and insights on the work undertaken regarding the subject model's revision and finalisation. Specifically, the provided feedback related to the identification (and establishment) of associations between the EIP-AGRI categories of topics and AGROVOC concepts.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review of the EIP-AGRI's taxonomy of agricultural topics Creation of links between the EIP-AGRI topics and the AGROVOC concepts
LFG	Feedback and insights given its leading role (as the organization in lead of WP4) in the digital platform's development.	Evaluation of the EUREKA FarmBook's subject model

Review of the EIP-AGRI's taxonomy of agricultural topics

A decision made at the outset of the process was to use the EIP-AGRI's taxonomy of agricultural topics (or "macro-categories") as the backbone of the subject model. The rationale behind this decision has been the existing familiarity of the agriculture and forestry community with it, as it is used for tagging digital information and content available from the EIP-AGRI database. However, the EIP-AGRI's taxonomy was created and revised on an ad-hoc basis, with no formal definitions available for the topic categories used.

The EIP-AGRI taxonomy of agricultural topics *before its update*

The EIP-AGRI taxonomy of agricultural topics *after its update*

Figure 5 – The EIP-AGRI macro-categories before and after the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy update (December 2021)

A review of the EIP-AGRI topic categories was therefore undertaken to propose definitions. IDELE was the partner organisation that led this specific part of the work. AKI provided insights and feedback. The proposed definitions (available in Annex II: “Definitions proposed for the EIP-AGRI macro-categories and their semantic networks”) allowed for the identification of the AGROVOC concepts that should be mapped to each of the EIP-AGRI macro-categories for creating a semantic network for each of them. It should be noted that the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy underwent an update during the revision and finalisation of the FarmBook’s subject model¹³ (December 2021), which involved EIP-AGRI abolishing some topic categories and introducing some new ones. Even though the subject model’s revision started earlier than the EIP-AGRI taxonomy’s update, the taxonomy updates were still considered for the finalisation of the EUREKA subject model. Figure 5 above illustrates the EIP-AGRI topic categories before and after the taxonomy’s update. The categories introduced in the updated taxonomy version are highlighted in grey colour (right-hand side of Figure 5).

Creation of links between the EIP-AGRI topics and the AGROVOC concepts and establishment of a semantic network for each topic in the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy

Each topic category of the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy was associated with a set of concepts from the AGROVOC thesaurus¹⁴ and labelled as having a broader, narrower, or similar scope to the EIP-AGRI’s topic categories associated with them. These types of relations have been encoded into the model using the skos:broader, skos:narrower, and skos:closeMatch properties defined in the SKOS specification. By associating each of the agricultural topics in the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy with AGROVOC concepts of a broader, narrower, and similar scope, there is potential to provide enhanced sets of results when users search for a specific topic. This way, solutions to exhaustive search needs (i.e., enabling the user to find anything available on a topic of interest) and exploratory seeking (providing some “good” results in cases where the user is not sure of what he/she is looking for) become available. The establishment of links between the topic categories of

¹³ The update of the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy of agricultural topics took place in November 2021.

¹⁴ <https://www.fao.org/agrovoc/>

the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy and AGROVOC concepts was undertaken by IDELE with the support of AKI. As an example, Table 8 below shows the AGROVOC concepts identified as broader, narrower, and similar to the “Landscape/land management” topic category of the EIP-AGRI taxonomy.

Table 8. Example showing AGROVOC concepts having a broader, narrower, and similar scope to the EIP-AGRI’s “Landscape/land management” topic category

AGROVOC concepts with a broader scope	Natural resources management
AGROVOC concepts with a narrower scope	Dryland management; Earthmoving; Integrated land management; Land clearing; Land concentration; Land conservation; Land rent; Land use; Pastoral lands; Sustainable land management
AGROVOC concepts with a similar scope	Environmental restoration; Land dispute; Land fragmentation

Apart from the identification of the links mentioned above, each of the EIP-AGRI categories of agricultural topics has been associated with one or more of the agricultural sectors (“Crop Farming”, “Livestock”, and “Forestry”) and/or cross-sectoral themes (“Environment”, “Society”, “Economics”) chosen as the top-level subjects for the description of content in the EUREKA FarmBook’s digital repository . These associations were identified based on the expertise of the project partners involved in this work and coded into the EUREKA FarmBook’s subject model using SKOS (specifically, the skos:related property). The AGROVOC concepts, agricultural sectors, and cross-sectoral themes associated with each of the EIP-AGRI taxonomy’s topic categories constitute the semantic network of the topic category. Figure 6 below shows the semantic network of the EIP-AGRI’s “Landscape/land management” topic category.

Figure 6 - The semantic network of the EIP-AGRI's "Landscape/land management" topic category

The AGROVOC concepts, agricultural sectors, and cross-sectoral themes associated with each of the EIP-AGRI's topic categories (and hence forming the EIP-AGRI topic category's semantic network) are provided in Annex II ("Definitions proposed for the EIP-AGRI macro-categories and their semantic networks").

Assembly and evaluation of the EUREKA FarmBook's subject model

The final assembly of the model of the agriculture- and forestry-related subjects involved the integration of the semantic networks of all the EIP-AGRI taxonomy's topic categories into a graph. Before proceeding to the graph's assembly, a thorough evaluation of the modelling work was undertaken by IFOAM EU. LFG provided feedback from a UX design perspective. The evaluation involved the review of the definitions provided to each of the EIP-AGRI agricultural topic categories, as well as the identification of the AGROVOC concepts, agricultural sectors, and cross-sectoral themes associated with each topic category in the EIP-AGRI taxonomy. Appropriate changes/adaptations and fine-tuning of the modelling work were made by returning to earlier steps of the process indicated by the arrows in Figure 4. The final graph version was developed in Protégé¹⁵ by AUA and MU. It is available in an RDF/ XML serialization format (under the CC-BY-4.0 license¹⁶) and can be accessed from the EUREKA project's community in Zenodo¹⁷.

¹⁵ <https://protege.stanford.edu/>

¹⁶ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

¹⁷ https://zenodo.org/communities/eureka_project_data/?page=1&size=20

3.3 FarmBook data repository technologies

A prior literature and user need analysis undertaken by EUREKA partners with the aim to determine the EUREKA FarmBook platform’s system requirements indicated the advantages of a centralised architecture compared to a federated architecture. As a result, the technical option that has been adopted to satisfy the specific requirement is **DSpace**¹⁸. According to its official documentation, DSpace is an “*out-of-the-box open-source software package for creating repositories focusing on delivering digital content to end users and providing a full set of tools for managing and preserving content within the application*”¹⁹. It is a full-stack web application comprising a database, storage manager, and front-end web interface. DSpace offers a solution going beyond a mere storage repository, as “*the stored metadata are kept accessible as technology formats and evolve over time*”.

DSpace is the most popular data repository solution with more than 2,000 installations worldwide. It has a vibrant community built around it²⁰, is flexible, and has the capacity to offer robust solutions to academic and research establishments as “*an open access institutional repository for managing and disseminating scholarly output*”, as well as other types of organisations for “*hosting and managing subject-based, dataset or media-based repositories*”. The integration with the OpenAIRE project is one of DSpace's core features²¹. Moreover, the specific framework provides solutions for the metadata storage along with the support and execution of search operations. Specifically, DSpace uses Fuseki (a triplestore for the storage of metadata) and Solr (for data indexing and the execution of searches). DSpace complies with all the available compatibility standards, such as OpenSearch, OpenURL, and RSS, and provides the additional advantage of a configurable database for managing all the available metadata. Table 9 presents DSpace’s features and their alignment with the identified requirements for the FarmBook digital repository²².

Table 9 - DSpace features and their alignment with the identified digital repository-related non-functional requirements

DSpace features	Non-functional system requirements they address
Open access repository for managing and delivering scholarly output, as well as hosting and managing subject-based, dataset or media-based repositories.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider a data repository software solution capable of storing the wide range of the MA project-related digital output categories that are available. The data repository software solution should provide video storage capabilities. The data repository software solution should allow for storing contact information of the creators of the MA project outputs.
Out-of-the-box open-source software package for providing a full set of tools for managing and preserving content within the application.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider an open-source repository solution allowing to scale-up and providing advanced data security and integrity options.
Functional preservation according to which files are kept accessible as technology formats, media and paradigms evolve over time for as many types of files as possible.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider an open-source repository solution allowing to scale-up and providing advanced data security and integrity options.

¹⁸ <https://duraspace.org/dspace/>

¹⁹ <https://duraspace.org/dspace/resources/technical-specifications/>

²⁰ <https://duraspace.org/dspace/about/features/>

²¹ <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSPACECRIS/OpenAIRE+Integration>

²² More details are available in the report of Deliverable 3.2 (“Data Repository Design and Data Pipeline Design”).

DSpace features	Non-functional system requirements they address
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The data repository software solution should allow for the metadata storage of external video links.
Framework for flexible and dynamically changeable data schemas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The data repository software solution should allow for the addition of unforeseen and unstructured metadata.

4 Ingestion of Knowledge Objects into the FarmBook data repository

The ingestion of Knowledge Objects (developed and initially disseminated by the various MAPs) into the EUREKA FarmBook’s digital repository has been a critical part of the implementation work related to the repository’s setup. The aim of this section is to provide the relevant details by focusing on: (i) the different means of ingesting Knowledge Objects into the repository (a brief introduction is made in Subsection 4.1 and further details are given in Subsections 4.3 and 4.4); (ii) the process of having the Knowledge Objects annotated with the appropriate metadata (Subsection 4.2); (iii) the measures taken to ensure the quality of the Knowledge Objects ingested into the repository (Subsection 4.5); (iv) quantitative information on the Knowledge Objects housed in the repository (Subsection 4.6); and (v) the repository’s FAIRness score (Subsection 4.7).

4.1 Batch ingestion of Knowledge Objects versus single Knowledge Object upload

There are two different scenarios considered in EUREKA regarding the supply of digital content and hence the ingestion of Knowledge Objects into the repository: (i) supply of Knowledge Objects from MA projects that have completed their lifecycle; and (ii) supply of Knowledge Objects from MA projects in progress. In the first case, a batch Knowledge Object upload process based on an ingestion pipeline is deployed. As regards the second case, there is the option of using an upload form for single Knowledge Object upload. Specifically, people involved in MA projects can use the form to upload Knowledge Objects, created in the MA project they represent, by providing the required metadata themselves. The ingestion pipeline design for the batch upload has been described in **Deliverable 3.2**, Section 4.2 (“Ingestion pipeline”). More details are provided in Subsection 4.3 of the present report. The upload form is presented in Subsection 4.4.

4.2 The Knowledge-Object annotation process

In the batch Knowledge Object upload/ingestion case, an important step related to the preparation of the Knowledge Objects to be ingested into the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository has been their annotation with metadata (see Subsection 3.1 of this report).

4.2.1 Assembly of the EUREKA annotation team

To execute this task, a team of annotators was assembled and trained. The team consisted of 14 members from various project partner organisations. The project partners that contributed with human resources to the annotation task were AUA, UGent, IDELE, ARC, LAAS, RAU, IFOAM EU, 3 APTA, AKI, and ZLTO. There was no requirement for the annotation team members to have previous experience in relevant tasks. Yet, it was made clear to partners during recruitment that a background knowledge/expertise in agriculture

or forestry would be an asset. Almost all members of the annotation team had a relevant background and expertise.

4.2.2 Training of the EUREKA annotation team

Two virtual training sessions took place on the 15th and 16th of November 2021 to introduce the scope and details of the annotation task to the members of the annotation team. The annotation team was split into two equally sized groups with the one receiving its training on the 15th of November and the other on the 16th of November. This arrangement was made with the aim to have groups of small size attending the sessions and therefore more flexibility and time for interaction and involvement in hands-on activities. A focal point of the training was the explanation of the importance of the process, i.e., the importance of having the Knowledge Objects described by metadata and carefully considering the values assigned to the metadata during the annotation. To this end, a detailed presentation and explanation of the metadata and the values to assign to them took place. Indicative examples were also provided. The material for the training was a slideshow presentation, which was developed by reusing part of the training material of EURAKNOS created for the same purpose. Q&A sessions in each training allowed questions and comments towards facilitating a better understanding of the requirements of the annotation task. Annotation mock-up activities took place to encourage the annotation team members to get a taste of the annotation task by becoming engaged in hands-on, practical examples. The design and delivery of the training (including the development of the support material available as part of the Annotation Pack²³) were implemented by AUA.

As a follow-up to the delivery of the training, the annotation team members were asked to evaluate the delivered training to enable conclusions about the training’s quality and clarity of provided instructions. The evaluation survey was created using Google Forms and sent to the training participants via email. The questions used to collect feedback and their type are listed in Table 10 below.

Table 10 - Questions included in the training’s evaluation survey and their types

#	Question included in the evaluation survey	Question type
1	<p>Indicate your level of agreement with the statements listed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The objectives of the training were clearly defined. • Participation and interaction were encouraged. • The instructions that have been provided were clear and relevant. • The training material that has been used was helpful. • The trainer was knowledgeable about the topics. • The trainer was well prepared. • The training objectives were met. • The time that has been allotted for the training workshop was sufficient. • The follow-up activities that have been proposed to take place are considered as adequate. 	<p>Closed-ended question (5-point Likert scale question used to collect feedback on participant opinions)</p>

²³ See subsection 4.2.3 (“Implementation of the annotation task and support”) for details.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The workshop and the training material that has been distributed will help to get adequately prepared for the annotation task. 	
2	What did you like the most about this training workshop?	Open-ended question
3	What aspects of the training workshop could have been better?	Open-ended question

The survey had a 64% response rate (i.e., 9 out of the 14 annotation team members provided responses). Table 11 lists the responses to Question #2 (“What did you like the most about this training workshop?”) and Question #3 (“What aspects of the training workshop could have been better?”).

Table 11 - Responses provided by the training participants to the survey’s open-ended questions

#	Question	Type	Provided response
1	What did you like the most about this training workshop?	Open-ended question	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trainer’s preparation and professionalism. The get your hands dirty activity. All the explanations about the different data we will have to fill in. Excellent, patient teacher/presenter who was well prepared and helpful. The testing part. Well organised and well implemented workshop, with interesting presentations.
2	What aspects of the training workshop could have been better?	Open-ended question	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Everything was great. I think that everything was well prepared. Nothing. Shift some time away from presentation and towards "getting hands dirty" earlier on, with more chance for feedback and questions (learn by doing).

Figure 7 below illustrates the feedback collected in respect to Question #1 of the survey.

Figure 7 - Feedback by the training participants to the evaluation items included in Question #1 of the survey

The feedback by the members of the annotation team/recipients of the training was positive and indicated a high degree of satisfaction. The trainees reported a delivery of clear instructions in the context of a well-structured training session. A comment mentioning that the allocation of more time to hands-on activities would enable a deeper understanding of the task has been carefully considered. The follow-up activities and the support material (see Subsection 4.2.3) helped towards solving questions and problems that arose during the implementation of the annotation task.

4.2.3 Implementation of the annotation task and support

The slideshow used for the training together with support material available in a digital form (the so-called “EUREKA Annotation Pack”) were set at the annotation team members’ disposal, after the completion of the training, through the EUREKA project’s SharePoint platform. Figure 8 below presents some indicative slides taken from the slideshow presentation used in the training sessions.

Objectives of the workshop

- Bring the members of the annotation team together and **establish a sense of belonging** to the annotation team, as well as **ownership of the task**.
- Establish a deep level of understanding** of the importance of having the FarmBook Knowledge Objects **correctly annotated** with metadata.
- Familiarise the members of the annotation team** with the set of the metadata defined in EUREKA and the values they may receive.
- Make concrete all the “technical” details** involved in the annotation process (the resources to be used, how to access the annotation resources, how to provide values to the metadata properties, follow-up and support, etc.).

The importance of annotation with metadata

- Metadata is defined as **information about data**.
- Metadata help provide **contextual information about data/digital objects**.
- The **identification and findability of data/digital objects is highly dependent on the accuracy of the metadata provided** (and thus, on how well the annotation with the necessary metadata, by human annotators, **has been implemented**).
- By having provided the “correct” metadata we **enable people to find what they are looking for!**

“Who is putting all the Math books in the Horror section?”

Figure 8 - Indicative set of slides of the slideshow presentation used for the orientation and training of the annotation team's members

The EUREKA Annotation Pack consisted of instructions provided in the form of documents presenting and explaining the predefined value lists that should be considered for the assignment of values to specific metadata properties (namely: “language(s)”, “intended purpose”, “geographic location(s)”, “type”, and “subject”). The slideshow presentation used in the training and the Annotation Pack are available in the EUREKA project’s community in Zenodo²⁴. The annotation started in the beginning of December 2021 and was completed by the middle of March 2022. The annotation team members were assigned Knowledge Objects to annotate from all categories from which Knowledge Objects were available as input to the repository (namely, documents, images, audios, videos, and presentations). Each member annotated on average nearly 63 of the Knowledge Objects available in the repository. The time needed for annotating a Knowledge Object ranged from 5 to 12 minutes. The annotation was implemented using a template (see Figure 9) having the form of a spreadsheet. Each spreadsheet column corresponded to a metadata property, whereas each row contained a Knowledge Object’s annotations with the appropriate metadata values. The templates were made available to the annotation team members via the project’s SharePoint platform. The spreadsheets containing the results of the annotations by each team member had a unique file name of the form: “Annotation_spreadsheet_<first_name_of_the_annotator>_<last_name_of_the_annotator>”.

#	title (*)	description (*)	keywords (*)	creator(s) (*)	language(s) (*)	date of completion	intended purpose (*)	geographic location(s)	Knowledge Object URL	category	type (*)
	(https://purl.org/dc/terms/title)	(https://schema.org/description)	(https://schema.org/keywords)	(http://purl.org/dc/terms/creator)	(https://schema.org/language)	(https://schema.org/dateCreated)	(https://schema.org/potentialAction)	(https://schema.org/contentLocation)	(https://schema.org/uri)	(*)	(http://purl.org/dc/terms/type)
1											
2											
3											
4											
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Row of the template:
Contains the metadata values assigned to a single Knowledge Object (i.e., the results of a single Knowledge Object's annotation)

Column of the template:
represents one of the metadata properties used to annotate the Knowledge Objects

Figure 9 - Screenshot of the template used to annotate the Knowledge Objects into the digital repository

²⁴ https://zenodo.org/communities/eureka_project_data/?page=1&size=20

The Knowledge Objects that have been annotated (and ingested into the repository) are those available from the sample of Thematic Networks²⁵ considered in EURAKNOS²⁶, a set of documents (namely, Practice Abstracts²⁷) made available from the AgriLink project²⁸, as well as videos and documents (namely, Practice Abstracts) created in the DISARM project²⁹. The Knowledge Objects of Thematic Networks considered in EURAKNOS had been already annotated as part of that project's work. To consider them as input for the FarmBook's repository, a re-annotation process had to be done given the differences in the two projects' data models and metadata sets³⁰. Subsection 4.6 ("Overview of the Knowledge Objects in the EUREKA FarmBook's repository") provides quantitative information on the number of Knowledge Objects housed in the digital repository and the MA projects they have been provided from. To better support the work of the annotation team, a channel was launched in the EUREKA project's Slack workspace. The channel was used to post announcements and start discussion threads on issues of relevance to the annotation.

4.2.4 Annotation quality check

An additional measure that was taken to ensure the quality and "correctness" of the annotation work involved a quality check executed by the AUA's annotation team members (having previous experience in such tasks). The quality check focused on: (i) confirming the assignment of values to all metadata for which value assignment was mandatory; (ii) confirming that the default value (suggested in the guidelines)³¹ was used in cases in which no indication about the metadata value to assign was evident from the Knowledge Object's content (such a case applied only to metadata for which the assignment of a metadata value was not mandatory; e.g., "geographic location(s)"); (iii) making sure that values were assigned to the metadata properties following the instructions provided in the training (e.g., use the ";" character to separate one metadata value from another in cases in which multiple values were allowed); (iv) checking the adherence of the annotation work to the guidelines for the assignment of metadata values from predefined lists (e.g., make sure that the value provided to the "subject" property was one of the values contained in the subject value list available in the Annotation Pack); and (v) layout issues.

4.3 Batch Knowledge-Object ingestion into the FarmBook data repository

For the ingestion of Knowledge Object batches into the FarmBook's digital repository, an ETL ("Extract – Transform - Load") process has been designed. The ETL is implemented as a Spring Boot microservice featuring a REST API for communication. The metadata assigned to the Knowledge Objects in the annotation process are provided in a CSV format, where each CSV file row provides the metadata of one Knowledge Object. The Knowledge Object itself can be supplied from an archive file format (e.g., ZIP) or through a URL available in the CSV file. The ETL process and the pipeline of the Knowledge Object batch

²⁵ Thematic Networks are a subcategory of MAPs.

²⁶ Details about the sample of Thematic Networks considered as sources of Knowledge Objects in the EURAKNOS project are available in Panoutsopoulos, H. et al. (2021b). D4.3: e-KRP documentation and guide. EURAKNOS project.

²⁷ According to the EUREKA project's data model, Practice Abstracts are a specific type of the Knowledge Objects belonging to the "Documents" category. Details are available in Panoutsopoulos, H. et al. (2021a). D3.2: Data Repository Design and Data Pipeline Design. EUREKA project.

²⁸ <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/>

²⁹ <https://disarmproject.eu/>

³⁰ Differences in the EURAKNOS's and EUREKA's data models are described in Section 3.4 ("The FarmBook data model") of the report of Deliverable 3.2 ("Data Repository Design and Data Pipeline Design").

³¹ The default value was "not available".

uploading is hosted inside a Digital Oceans droplet³², which is a virtual machine that can adjust based on the needs of the project.

The virtual machine that will be used, has a Linux based operating system (Ubuntu). All the required services for running the ingestion process, as they are described in the following paragraphs, will be installed in the specific machine. Furthermore, as the FarmBook repository is running as a web-app, all the user interaction is done through the web platform and no installation is necessary to interact with the FarmBook repository.

An illustrative example is shown in the sequence diagram in Figure 10 below. It is based on the exploitation of the web crawling application created for the EURAKNOS project, which monitors the data repositories of Thematic Networks (MA projects in the case of EUREKA) and gathers new binary data and metadata. This information is curated and extended by manual annotations and stored as CSV data (as part of the work involved in the “Knowledge Object annotation” step of the batch upload scenario). Periodically, this data is retrieved by the ETL service, the binary data is downloaded, and the data is transformed to be DSpace compliant. Finally, data is stored on local storage reachable by DSpace.

Figure 10 - Sequence diagram displaying the ETL process from a thematic network webpage to local storage

The created CSV file is uploaded to the ETL process through a POST request that is done to the address of the droplet that hosts the ETL. After loading the CSV and binary files of the Knowledge Object, a

³² <https://www.digitalocean.com/products/droplets>

checksum³³ is created and added to the available metadata. This addition safeguards the repository from any corrupted binary data but also allows it to determine if any identical files exist. The specific queries are performed on the document store to ensure that the Knowledge Objects that will be uploaded in the future do not already exist in the system (through the validation done from the ETL process; see Figure 11 below). Such a function serves as the means to ensure data quality.

```
private boolean objectExists(String query) {
    WebClient.RequestHeadersSpec<> uri = webClient.get()
        .uri(builder -> builder.path(dspaceConfig.getDiscoverySearchPath())
            .queryParams("query", query)
            .queryParams("dsoType", "item")
            .build());
    try {
        WebClient.ResponseSpec response = uri.retrieve();
        ExistenceResponseDto existenceResponseDto = response.bodyToMono(ExistenceResponseDto.class).block();
        if(existenceResponseDto.getTotalElements() > 0){
            return true;
        } else {
            return false;
        }
    } catch(WebClientException e){
        log.error("Error requesting knowledge objects upload.", e);
    }
    return false;
}
```

Figure 11 - Function for the verification of a Knowledge Object's unique existence

In addition, a "filesize" metadata field is automatically calculated and added to the available metadata based on the binary data that are provided to the ETL for the knowledge object, as can be seen in Figure 12.

```
private void addChecksum(KnowledgeObject knowledgeObject) {
    try (InputStream is = Files.newInputStream(Paths.get(knowledgeObject.getFilePath().toString()))) {
        String checksum = org.apache.commons.codec.digest.DigestUtils.md5Hex(is);
        knowledgeObject.getOptionalMetaData().put("knowledgeobject.checksum", checksum);
    } catch (IOException e) {
        log.error("Unable to generate checksum for file: {}", knowledgeObject.getFilePath(), e);
    }
}

private void addFilesize(KnowledgeObject knowledgeObject) {
    long filesize = FileUtils.sizeOf(knowledgeObject.getFilePath().toFile());
    knowledgeObject.getOptionalMetaData().put("creativework.filesize", String.valueOf(filesize));
}
```

Figure 12 - Functions for automatically adding Checksum and File size metadata for Knowledge Objects

As a preparatory step to loading the Knowledge Objects into DSpace, all data is initially converted into a proprietary Simple Archive Format³⁴ required for the DSpace registration. This process results in the storage of all entries and metadata, in the supplied CSV, on the local file system. Specifically, each entry produces its own directory. This directory contains the binary data for the entry as well as XML files

³³ According to Wikipedia (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Checksum>), "checksum" is the term used to denote "a small-sized block of data derived from another block of digital data for the purpose of detecting errors that may have been introduced during its transmission or storage." Checksums are "often used to verify data integrity but are not relied upon to verify data authenticity."

³⁴ <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSDOC5x/Importing+and+Exporting+Items+via+Simple+Archive+Format>

containing the entries' descriptive metadata. Once all data is stored locally in the desired format, data is ingested into the repository. The registration of items into DSpace occurs on a configurable time interval during which the local file storage, containing the prepared folders with binary and XML data, is read. Specifically, a scheduled CRON job is triggered for the items to be ingested into DSpace. However, as an alternative, there is also the option of triggering the ingestion before the scheduled time by running an available script.

Data is stored differently depending on its modality. Binary data is stored in a fully transaction-safe way on local storage. System information on the Knowledge Object, such as IDs, are stored in the relational PostgreSQL built into DSpace. The metadata storage takes place in the Solr document storage instance. Furthermore, all metadata are converted to RDF triples. This process takes place by a configurable mapping, which converts each metadata key-value pair to a corresponding triple in RDF. The resulting triples are stored in the Fuseki triplestore. As a general note, the batch uploading of Knowledge Objects via the ETL has been a convenient solution as more content can be simultaneously uploaded to DSpace, but it relies on the administrators of the application to upload the available CSV files through the created request. It is important to mention that all the developed code and processes are available from the EUREKA project's community page on Zenodo³⁵. Parts of the code that were used during the development, can be found in Annex IV.

4.4 Single Knowledge Object upload

In addition to the batch upload of available data, there is also the option for independent contributors to use an upload form (found [here](#)). The form is a user-friendly option to enrich the content of the FarmBook. However, compared to the ETL process (as described in 4.3), the possible downside or limitation is that only one Knowledge Object can be uploaded at a time.

The form has been developed with the help of the work and input of MU. Regarding the used technologies, the upload form, and the login page (see Figure 13 below) are created using React³⁶ and the uploaded Knowledge Objects are passed and modified at the Spring REST API, as described for the implementation of the ETL in Section 4.3 ("Batch Knowledge Object ingestion into the FarmBook data repository").

³⁵ https://zenodo.org/communities/eureka_project_data/?page=1&size=20

³⁶ <https://reactjs.org/>

The screenshot shows the FarmBook login interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the 'EU FARMBOOK Pilot version' logo, a 'Topics' dropdown menu, a search bar with the placeholder text 'Search for articles, experts, threads...', and links for 'About us', 'Help', and a 'LOG IN' button. Below the navigation bar is a grey header with the 'EU FARMBOOK' logo. The main content area contains a message: 'In order to upload objects through the form, a separate privileged account is currently required. Please contact us at eufarmbook@ugent.be for more information.' Below this message are two input fields: 'USERNAME' and 'PASSWORD'. At the bottom of the form is a dark green 'LOG IN' button.

Figure 13 - Log in form to access the form for uploading a Knowledge Object to the FarmBook's repository

As a first step for the uploading of a Knowledge Object using the form, the user needs to come in contact with the admin team of the FarmBook platform to acquire an account for using the upload form. Without the specific credentials, the user will not be able to have access; this is necessary for database security reasons. It is worth mentioning that at present the credentials of the account that users acquire when signing up in the FarmBook platform are different from the account and credentials that should be used to have access to the upload form.

After the user has successfully logged in, it is required to provide values for all the required fields as they are shown in the form (see Figure 14 below). These fields correspond to a Knowledge Object's metadata. To provide the binary data of the Knowledge Object, the user must provide either a URL to the Knowledge Object file or upload the file itself from their local folders.

Knowledge Object

Yes, I will provide the URL to the object

KNOWLEDGE OBJECT URL*

the URL to the knowledge object
Please provide a value for this field

TITLE*

The title of the knowledge object
Please provide a value for this field

DESCRIPTION*

A short (500 character or around 100 words) summary of the knowledge object.
Please provide a value for this field

PROJECT NAME*

The project under which the knowledge object was created
Please provide a value for this field

PROJECT ACRONYM*

The acronym of the project under which the knowledge object was created
Please provide a value for this field

PROJECT URL*

The main URL of the project under which the knowledge object was created
Please provide a value for this field

Figure 14 – Fields that are required to be filled in with values when using the upload form to provide a Knowledge Object to the FarmBook’s repository

The user must provide a title, a description with a 500-character limit and information about the source project’s name, acronym, and URL. As a next step, the user can select one or more high-level subjects (i.e., “Crop farming”, “Livestock”, “Forestry”, “Environment”, “Society”, and “Economics”) and at minimum two second-level subjects (i.e., from the EIP-AGRI “macro-categories”) based on the selections at the higher subject level. The uploaded Knowledge Object should also have the object’s Category and Type defined, as well as be characterised by one or more Keywords, Creators and Languages that correspond to it. The user has the option to select a license related to the Knowledge Object or even provide a license URL not included in the available list. The next fields to be filled are the Completion Date and the Geographical Location (see Figure 15 below). For the Geographical Location, there is the option to select multiple places that are mentioned in the Knowledge Object. On the other hand, for the Completion Date, the user can either define the exact date that the Knowledge Object was completed by selecting from a calendar or provide only the year of the Knowledge Object’s completion. The last step is to press the submit button to transfer the content to the repository. If all the fields were filled correctly, the Knowledge Object will be successfully uploaded. If something is missing or incorrect, the upload process will not continue to the next step and an error message will be shown on the screen for the field values that need to be modified. The code developed for the creation and deployment of the form is available at the project’s community page on Zenodo³⁷. Parts of the code that were used during the development, can be found in Annex IV.

³⁷ https://zenodo.org/communities/eureka_project_data/?page=1&size=20

Completion Date

I have the exact date available

– select an option –
I only know the year of completion
I have the exact date available

The day on which work on the knowledge object was completed

mm/dd/yyyy

Please provide a value for this field

Geographical Location(s)

Please select all countries referenced in the knowledge object's contents.

+ ADD ITEM

SUBMIT

Figure 15 – The EU FarmBook Knowledge-Object upload form's Completion Date and Geographical Location options

4.5 Knowledge Object quality assurance

As mentioned earlier, digital content can be provided to the FarmBook either by means of a single-object upload, using a dedicated upload form, or as part of a batch upload process. In both cases, there is a need for measures ensuring the quality of the Knowledge Objects. Regarding the batch upload, quality aspects have been considered as part of the work of the annotation team. Quality checks have been made by the annotation team regarding the identification of: (i) corrupted/damaged digital files whose content could not be accessed; and (ii) Knowledge Objects of content not relevant to the audience of the platform (e.g., the agenda of a conference organised by a MA project). The identification of the relevance of a Knowledge Object's content has been achieved by having the annotators skimming through the Knowledge Object's content. Skimming through a Knowledge Object's content was a step taken to also make decisions about the values to assign to specific metadata (i.e., the "intended purpose", "geographic location(s)", "type", and "subject" metadata properties).

Regarding the supply of Knowledge Objects from MA project representatives using the upload form, the issue of quality has been considered with respect to both the Knowledge Object and the metadata values assigned to it. In the latter case, the metadata values' quality is ensured by the intuitive layout of the upload form, the hints available in the upload form, and the accompanying user guide to the upload form³⁸ providing detailed instructions about the assignment of metadata values and the upload of the Knowledge Object. However, because the final development and testing of the upload form was completed close to the end of the project, no Knowledge Objects had been uploaded in this way by the time this report was drafted (and instead were processed via batch upload). Hence, there has not yet been a need to check

³⁸ The upload form's user guide is available at the EUREKA project's official website.

the quality of Knowledge Objects provided independently by “external contributors”. The platform and the upload form will be available to use after the project’s end. Eventually, there will indeed be content in the FarmBook platform provided by external contributors. Guaranteeing the quality of the Knowledge Objects provided by MA project representatives (one group of platform users) is important for ensuring a high impact for the FarmBook platform. To this end, monitoring mechanisms have been considered to enable regular inspections of the quality of the Knowledge Objects in the platform. More specifically, a data stewardship team will have the responsibility to check the quality of Knowledge Objects submitted by the platform users through the upload form. The data stewardship team’s members will come from the partner organisation in charge of the digital repository’s development (AUA) and the coordinator of the EUREKA (UGent). The team will assume the responsibility of regular quality checks for a period of six months till the launch of the follow-up project³⁹.

4.6 Overview of the Knowledge Objects in the FarmBook’s repository

The Knowledge Objects housed in the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository at the time this report was drafted come from the Smart-AKIS⁴⁰, FERTINNOWA⁴¹, SKIN⁴², SheepNet⁴³, Inno4Grass⁴⁴, 4D4F⁴⁵, and AFINET⁴⁶ projects (also considered as input sources for the repository of the prototype e-KRP built in EURAKNOS), the EURAKNOS⁴⁷ project, as well as the DISARM⁴⁸, AgriLink⁴⁹, and AE4EU⁵⁰ MA projects. To help establish bridges between EUREKA and its follow-up project (the EU-FarmBook project funded under the HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-24 topic), a process of making contacts with and attracting the interest of EU-funded R&D projects, to contribute with the supply of Knowledge Objects produced by them, will be in progress for a period of six months (till the follow-up project’s launch, planned for the 1st of August 2022). Consequently, digital content from more projects will be provided to, and become available from, the EUREKA FarmBook digital platform in the coming period. In this section, information about the Knowledge Objects in the digital repository (by the time of drafting this report) is provided. This information offers insights into the total number of Knowledge Objects in the repository, the number of Knowledge Objects per project, the number of Knowledge Objects per category (i.e., documents, presentations, images, videos, and audios) and type, as well as the temporal distribution of the Knowledge Object’s completion dates, the subjects of the Knowledge Objects, the languages in which content is available, the geographic locations (i.e., countries) associated with the Knowledge Object’s content, and the file formats.

The number of Knowledge Objects in the FarmBook’s repository (by the time of drafting this deliverable report) was **880**. Table 12 below illustrates the number of Knowledge Object’s available per project.

³⁹ The EU-FarmBook project funded under the HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-24 topic.

⁴⁰ <https://www.smart-akis.com/>

⁴¹ <https://www.fertinnowa.com/project/>

⁴² <http://www.shortfoodchain.eu/>

⁴³ <http://www.sheepnet.network/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.inno4grass.eu/en/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.4d4f.eu/>

⁴⁶ <https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/afinet>

⁴⁷ <https://euraknos.eu/>

⁴⁸ <https://disarmproject.eu/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.ae4eu.eu/>

Table 12 - Number of Knowledge Objects per project in the EUREKA FarmBook's repository

Project	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository	Project	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
SheepNet	147	SKIN	66
DISARM	114	Inno4Grass	63
4D4F	111	AFINET	45
Smart-AKIS	109	EURAKNOS	21
AgriLink	96	OK-NET Arable	7
FERTINNOWA	68	AE4EU	1

Table 13 lists the number of Knowledge Objects per Knowledge Object category (i.e., documents, videos, presentations, images, and audios).

Table 13 - Number of Knowledge Objects per category in the EUREKA FarmBook's repository

Knowledge Object category	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository	Knowledge Object category	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
Documents	494	Audios	21
Videos	253	Presentations	10
Images	41		

To further elaborate on the information available in the above table, Table 14,

Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository	Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
Practice Abstracts	217	Flyers	5
Factsheets	114	Technical/technology articles	3
Guides	19	Case studies	3
Deliverable reports	18	Technical information/specifications cards	2
Policy briefs	14	Journal articles	2
Reports/papers	11	Books	1
Newsletters	9	Milestone reports	1
Booklets	6	Press releases	1
Brochures	6	Tutorials	1

Table 15,

Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository	Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
Informative presentations	6	Guides	1
Educational/training presentations	2	Decision-making presentations	1

Table 16,

Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository	Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
Infographics	33	Static figures/images	2

Charts/graphs	2
---------------	---

Table 17, and Table 18 present the **number of Knowledge Objects per type and per category**⁵¹.

Table 14 - Number of Knowledge objects per document type in the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository

Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository	Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
Practice Abstracts	217	Flyers	5
Factsheets	114	Technical/technology articles	3
Guides	19	Case studies	3
Deliverable reports	18	Technical information/specifications cards	2
Policy briefs	14	Journal articles	2
Reports/papers	11	Books	1
Newsletters	9	Milestone reports	1
Booklets	6	Press releases	1
Brochures	6	Tutorials	1

Table 15 - Number of Knowledge objects per presentation type in the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository

Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository	Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
Informative presentations	6	Guides	1
Educational/training presentations	2	Decision-making presentations	1

Table 16 - Number of Knowledge objects per image type in the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository

Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository	Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
Infographics	33	Static figures/images	2
Charts/graphs	2		

Table 17 - Number of Knowledge objects per video type in the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository

Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository	Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
Educational/training videos	71	Event capturing videos	7
Testimonials	38	Cases studies	5
presentation/live talk capturing videos	35	Documentary videos	5
Interview videos	26	Webinars	5
Product/feature review videos	23	Tutorials	4
Tutorial/how-to videos	17	Simulation videos	2
Guides	9	Vlogs	1

⁵¹ A detailed discussion on the types of Knowledge Objects considered per Knowledge Object category in the EUREKA data model is available in the report of Deliverable 3.2 (“Data Repository Design and Data Pipeline Design”).

Table 18 - Number of Knowledge objects per audio type in the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository

Knowledge Object type	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
Interviews	14
Question-and-Answer podcasts	7

The subjects addressed in the content of the Knowledge Objects housed in the EUREKA FarmBook’s digital repository are shown in Table 19 below. The figures in the table relate to the top-level subjects (i.e., Crop farming, Livestock, Forestry, Society, Environment, & Economics) addressed by the Knowledge Objects in the digital repository.

Table 19 - Number of Knowledge Objects available per subject

Subject	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository	Subject	Number of Knowledge Objects in the repository
Crop Farming	296	Society	188
Livestock	512	Environment	103
Forestry	46	Economics	104

Some further insights about the Knowledge Objects in the FarmBook repository are enabled by Figure 16, Figure 17, Figure 18, and Figure 19 showing the temporal distribution of the Knowledge Objects’ dates of completion, the languages of the Knowledge Objects’ content, the geographic locations associated with the content of the Knowledge Objects, and the Knowledge Objects’ purpose of creation respectively.

Figure 16 - Distribution of the years of creation of the Knowledge Objects into the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository

Figure 17 – Languages in which the content of the EUREKA FarmBook repository’s Knowledge Objects is available

Figure 18 - Geographic locations (i.e., countries) to which the content of the Knowledge Objects relates

Figure 19 - Purposes for which the Knowledge Objects have been developed and their respective numbers

As shown in Figure 16 above, most of the Knowledge Objects stored in the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository have been published from 2017 and on. So, the information/data available from the Knowledge Objects in the digital repository can be considered up-to-date and capable of covering the need of users to access digital content conveying contemporary solutions and best agricultural/forestry practices. In addition, as

made evident from the chart illustrated in Figure 17, English is the predominant language in which digital content is available. French, Dutch, Romanian, and Italian are the next most frequent languages regarding the availability of digital content from the FarmBook digital repository. The information available from the diagram depicted in Figure 18 makes clear that Belgium, France, Italy, the Netherlands, and Spain are the countries to which the solutions/practices mentioned in the digital repository’s Knowledge Objects mostly relate. Finally, dissemination, education/training, and communication are the purposes for which most of the Knowledge Objects available in the EUREKA FarmBook’s digital repository have been developed.

4.7 Evaluation of the FAIRness of the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository

Following the practice already adopted in EURAKNOS⁵², the FAIRness of the FarmBook’s digital repository has been evaluated using SATIFYD (Self-Assessment Tool to Improve the FAIRness of Your Dataset)⁵³. SATIFYD is a FAIRness evaluation tool developed by DANS⁵⁴ (the Data Archiving and Network Services) and is made up of 12 assessment items split into four sections (one section per FAIR principle with three items included in each section). SATIFYD provides an evaluation score for each of the FAIR principles and a final “FAIRness score”. Table 20 lists the evaluation items available in SATIFYD (to assess the compliance with each FAIR principle), the list of responses to select from per evaluation item, the responses provided to evaluate the FAIRness of the FarmBook’s repository, and the scores achieved as part of the evaluation of the FAIRness of the prototype e-KRP built in the EURAKNOS project to showcase the progress achieved in EUREKA. The full report of the evaluation of the FAIRness of the FarmBook repository is available in Annex III (“EUREKA FarmBook repository’s FAIRness evaluation report”).

Table 20. Results of the EUREKA FarmBook digital repository’s FAIRness evaluation

	Assessment item	Potential responses	Response provided	FarmBook repository score	e-KRP score
FINDABLE	Did you provide sufficient metadata (information) about your data for others to find, understand and reuse your data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rich metadata with as much information as possible. Required metadata fields and some additional fields. Minimal metadata but only required fields No metadata. 	Rich metadata with as much information as possible.	100%	55%
	Did you use standards such as controlled vocabularies, taxonomies (thesauri) or ontologies to describe your dataset?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Controlled vocabularies. Taxonomies (thesauri). Ontologies. There are no standards for my discipline. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Controlled vocabularies. Taxonomies (thesauri). Ontologies. 		
	Did you provide rich and detailed additional documentation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Readme file. Versioning. Provenance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Readme file. Versioning. Provenance. 		

⁵² A discussion on the traction that the compliance to the FAIR principles has attracted in the past few years and the results of the evaluation of the prototype e-KRP’s FAIRness are available in Panoutsopoulos, H. et al. (2021b). D4.3: e-KRP documentation and guide. EURAKNOS project.

⁵³ <https://dans.knaw.nl/nl>

⁵⁴ <https://satisfyd.dans.knaw.nl/>

	Assessment item	Potential responses	Response provided	FarmBook repository score	e-KRP score
ACCESSIBLE	Is the metadata publicly accessible even if the data is no longer available?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I can't find this information in EASY. 	Yes	75%	50%
	Does your dataset contain personal data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No 	No		
	Which of the usage licenses provided by EASY did you choose to comply with the access rights attached to the data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open access (CC0). • Restricted access. • Embargo. • Other access. • I don't know which of these licenses apply to my data. 	Other access. ⁵⁵		
INTEROPERABLE	Are the data in your dataset stored in preferred formats?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All the data are in preferred formats. • Some of the data are in preferred formats. • None of the data are in preferred formats. • I don't know what preferred formats are. 	All the data are in preferred formats.	58%	50%
	Do you link to other (meta)data and is this (meta)data online resolvable?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and these are online accessible. • Yes, but they are not online accessible. • No. 	No		
	Did you provide contextual information about your dataset?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persistent identifiers. • Reference to other datasets. • Reference to publications. • No contextual metadata. 	Persistent identifiers.		
REUSABLE	What kind of information did you provide about the provenance of your data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Origin of data. • Citations for reused data. • Workflow description for collecting data (machine readable). • Processing history of data. • Version history of data. 	Origin of data.	55%	37%
	Which usage license provided by EASY did choose for your dataset?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open access (CC0). • Restricted access. • Embargo. • Other access. • I don't know which of these licenses apply to my data. 	Other access.		
	Does your (meta)data meet domain standards?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain standards in metadata. • Minimal domain standards and minimal generic standards. • Generic standards. • No standards used. 	Domain standards in metadata.		
Total FAIRness score				72%	54%

⁵⁵ The license assigned by default to the Knowledge Object's in the EUREKA FarmBook's digital repository (at least in cases in which the Knowledge Objects had not been assigned a license by their creators) is the Creative Commons [CC BY 4.0 license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). This is the license type adopted for the distribution of digital material of the same categories and similar types to the FarmBook digital repository's Knowledge Objects in the cases of other widely used repositories as well (e.g., Zenodo).

The evaluation results provide clear indications of the improvement in the FAIRness performance of the FarmBook repository by achieving a FAIRness evaluation score 18% higher than that of the EURAKNOS's prototype e-KRP (72% as opposed to 54% achieved in EURAKNOS). As made evident in the above table, the EUREKA FarmBook repository has achieved higher scores for each FAIR principle, which are on average 24% higher compared to the scores of the e-KRP⁵⁶. The highest improvement has been achieved for the “Findable” principle (45% increase), whereas the smallest improvement relates to the “Interoperable” principle with an 8% increase in the assessed performance. This overall improvement has been achieved as the result of the work in EUREKA regarding the repository's conceptual design and data modelling, as part of addressing the following EURAKNOS recommendations⁵⁷:

- “Elaborate on the technical design of the e-KRP:
 - The work in EUREKA regarding data modelling needs to build upon the results of EURAKNOS and the adherence to the FAIR data principles (i.e., the development of a FAIR digital repository) needs to be considered as an effort in progress.
 - EUREKA needs to undertake a further investigation of ontologies and controlled vocabularies to consider for defining the entities, concepts, and properties to include in its revised data model. This will allow the creation of a robust (in terms of coverage of the needs for describing the data objects), flexible (able to be extended in the future), and elegant (regarding trade-offs between size and descriptiveness) model.”
- “Updates to the EURAKNOS metadata set:
 - Consider updates reflecting the changes in the data model (compared to the EURAKNOS data model) because of the further identification and consideration of vocabularies and ontologies for the needs of describing model-related elements (entities, relations, and properties).”

The results of the FarmBook repository's FAIRness evaluation are indicative of the design considerations and actions that need to be taken when developing repositories for enabling a “Findable”, “Accessible”, “Interoperable”, and “Reusable” approach to digital content availability. The work in EUREKA paves the way towards practices enabling the adherence to the FAIR data principles, in the context of agriculture, especially when compared to the FAIRness of other agriculture- and forestry-related repositories of digital information and content. As reported in Deliverable 3.1⁵⁸, the investigation of the degree of adherence of a sample of Knowledge Objects coming from the repositories of 19 MA projects revealed that 61% of them performed poorly in the evaluation of the “Findable” principle, 93% of the Knowledge Objects had an average or poor performance in relation to the “Interoperable” principle, and 75% performed poorly in the “Reusable” principle. Only in the case of the “Accessible” principle, the evaluation results revealed a more favourable performance (61% of the investigated Knowledge Objects). Based on this evidence, it can be concluded that the work for the design and development of the EUREKA FarmBook's repository

⁵⁶ In both cases (i.e., EUREKA and EURAKNOS), the evaluation of the FAIRness has been based on the same tool (i.e., the [SATIFYD FAIRness evaluation tool](#)).

⁵⁷ These recommendations are available (and discussed in detail) in Section 12 (“Conclusions and next steps”) of the report of Deliverable 4.3 of EURAKNOS (Panoutsopoulos et al., 2021b).

⁵⁸ Bolzonella P. et al. (2021). D3.1 Data Selection and Data Quality Assessment Report. EUREKA project.

has laid the foundations for a FAIRer management of agriculture- and forestry-related digital content and information, enabling broader and more rapid knowledge sharing.

5 User authentication and “Experts”

To provide data security mechanisms, user authentication has been considered in the EUREKA FarmBook repository. Currently, there are two cases for which credentials are needed. The first case (expected to be by far the most common) is simply the login credentials needed if a user wishes to utilise the social or interactive features of the FarmBook platform itself (described below). Here, the registration is done by the users (without needing to contact the platform’s admin team) through the Sign-Up form (see Figure 20 below). Authenticated users then have the option of posting a comment on “liking” or “downvoting” content, as well as filling out personal profiles with more information about themselves.

The screenshot shows the 'Sign Up' form on the EUREKA FarmBook Pilot version website. The form includes the following fields and elements:

- Username *
- Your Age
- First Name *
- Last Name *
- E-mail Address *
- Password *
- Your Profession (Please select a value)
- Your Main Interest (Please select a value)
- I Accept The [Terms And Conditions](#) *
- Sign up button
- COOKIES notice: This website uses cookies in order to provide the most relevant information. Please cookies for optimal performance. [More info](#) →

Figure 20 – The FarmBook digital platform’s sign-up form

The second log-in account is required for those who wish to contribute individual Knowledge Objects via the FarmBook’s upload form (details are provided in Section 4.4). To acquire the necessary credentials, a user must contact the DSpace admin team. The created account will provide the role of the author to the user and will be linked with the DSpace system, where all the data ingestion processes are taking place. After successfully acquiring the log-in account, and by having access to upload form, a user takes the steps described in Section 4.4 (“Single Knowledge Object upload”) for the needs of Knowledge Object ingestion.

In the current EUREKA implementation of the FarmBook, all information about created users are stored in the userbase of the Drupal system, which is different from the DSpace userbase. The two different userbases are automatically connected to each other to share credentials between the systems and are kept up to date through a daily scheduled synchronisation of Knowledge Objects between Drupal and

DSpace, during which the admins of Drupal receive a list of authors (of FarmBook content) that are stored in DSpace. The received DSpace user information is matched with the userbase of Drupal. If a connection is found between the two userbases, the linked user acquires the role of “Expert” in Drupal, and therefore in the FarmBook platform. If there is no user match, a new “Expert” profile is created in Drupal’s userbase, but with no connection to an already existing user. The association of a user account with an “Expert” profile allows for multiple Knowledge Objects to be associated with that user, providing increased visibility of the user through the different Knowledge Objects.

6 Testing the FarmBook digital repository

To better justify the decision of proceeding with Drupal as an additional “middle” layer between DSpace and the user interface in the FarmBook platform’s technology stack, some test cases were performed. Not only from a functional point of view, but also from the perspective of performance. The synchronisation between DSpace and Drupal is performed daily to acquire the latest Knowledge Objects available for the FarmBook. Based on the tests that have been implemented, with the current setup and hosting, syncing one (1) Knowledge Object between the two repositories (i.e., Drupal and DSpace) requires approximately 15 to 20 seconds. This latency in the acquisition of a Knowledge Object relates to the need of fetching the translations for each Knowledge Object in 16 languages⁵⁹.

The process of synchronisation can be improved by raising the hosting platform’s technical specs, but that would impact the cost of the EUREKA FarmBook digital repository’s deployment. The specifications of the current hosting are 2 CPUs and 4 GB RAM. As an alternative, there is an asynchronous process between DSpace and Drupal taking place every night at 03.00 AM (CET/CEST). This time is chosen to minimise the chance that users are affected by the impact of synchronisation between the two repositories, which causes slower loading of pages and search results. For the current number of Knowledge Objects housed in the FarmBook’s repository at the time of drafting the present report, the entire synchronisation process requires approximately 3 hours and 20 minutes.

On top of synchronisation testing, there have also been tests on the load that end-users create (see Table 21 below).

Table 21 - User searches on the FarmBook platform and response time for each query

Test	Remarks	Language	Number of samples	Average response time
1	Search, no filters	EN	100	109ms
2	Search, filtering “cow” with includes	EN	100	80ms
3	Search, filtering “vache” with includes	FR	100	58ms
4	Detail page 1	EN	100	43ms
5	Detail page 2	EN	100	36ms
6	Detail page 3	FR	100	41ms

The response time for each query is 200 to 500 times faster with the Drupal layer compared to acquiring the content directly from DSpace. In terms of performance, the specific results are a major improvement in UX. Furthermore, based on the current results, it can be concluded that the FarmBook infrastructure

⁵⁹ <https://www.deepl.com/docs-api/>

can easily handle 100 requests/second. If a user makes 3 to 5 requests per minute, the current hosting-configuration of the platform can guarantee a performant experience for 3000 concurrent users on the platform. When reaching such numbers of users in the future, it is recommended to further monitor the performance of the platform but also implement auto-scaling of the infrastructure to be able to handle peak-moments in load without raising the costs at all times.

7 Search capabilities and user guide

Whenever a user performs a search action the query execution takes place inside Drupal. For searching and data indexing, a SOLR implementation of Drupal is used. The SOLR implementation is also available in DSpace. However, different advantages have led to the decision of choosing indexing and searching inside Drupal. First, the performance is improved if the search query and retrieval of the content is performed inside Drupal by comparing it to the same actions performed in DSpace, as it is described in the tests in Section 6 (“Testing the FarmBook digital repository”). Furthermore, an automatic translation feature of Drupal is used for the Knowledge Objects that are acquired from DSpace and all translations are hosted in Drupal, a feature which is not available in DSpace. Thus, the user has the option to search the FarmBook content in different languages, returning the same results auto translated by DeepL (see Section 6). In more detail, the search queries of the users are always performed in the same language that they selected from the menu and only that language version of the (auto-translated) metadata is queried. This can in some cases lead to poor results in languages other than English (the default language for all the primary Knowledge-Object metadata), either if the auto-translations are not accurate or not what is commonly used for a given subject. The next major update of the FarmBook platform in the follow-up project⁶⁰ will take these disadvantages into account, and it is the aim of the project coordinators and the development team to design technical solutions addressing this limitation and expand the multilingual performance and user-friendliness.

A final advantage of the Drupal middle layer stems from the fact that a search query is performed not only across all the available Knowledge Objects, but also the information that is stored regarding “Experts”, “Comments”, and “Threads & discussions”. The latter content is not available in DSpace, so the option of searching inside Drupal is more efficient and richer in terms of provided results.

The non-functional system requirements that have been considered to make decisions and choices about the development of the FarmBook platform’s search engine are listed in Table 22 below⁶¹.

Table 22 – Non-functional requirements of the FarmBook platform’s system related to the development of the search engine and their source

Source of non-functional requirements	Non-functional system requirements
Non-functional requirements derived from the results reported in Deliverable 1.4 ⁶²	Consider a search engine software solution capable of providing a range of information search and retrieval options based on fit-for-purpose content indexing.

⁶⁰ The EU-FarmBook project funded under the HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-24 topic.

⁶¹ The information provided in Table 22 has been taken from the report of Deliverable 3.2 (“Data Repository Design and Data Pipeline Design”), and more specifically from Section 3.1.3 (“Non-functional requirements”).

⁶² Čandek Potokar et al. (2020).

Feedback from the interviews in Task 1.3 ⁶³	Consider a search engine software solution capable of providing a range of information search and retrieval options based on fit-for-purpose content indexing.
Challenges faced by end-users in their information seeking and problem-solving “journeys”	Consider a search engine software solution capable of providing a range of information search and retrieval options based on fit-for-purpose content indexing. Consider a search engine software solution capable of storing and serving rich metadata.
Emotions faced by end-users in their information seeking and problem-solving “journeys”	Consider a search engine capable of faceted search. Consider a search engine solution capable of providing a range of information search and retrieval options based on fit-for-purpose content indexing.
Input collected from the one-to-one, online interviews conducted in Task 2.2 ⁶⁴	Consider a search engine software solution able to provide a range of information search and retrieval options based on fit-for-purpose content indexing.
Information related to personas	Consider a search engine software solution capable of providing a range of information search and retrieval options based on fit-for-purpose content indexing.
Non-functional requirements derived from the expert webinars conducted in Task 3.1 ⁶⁵	Consider a search engine software solution capable of providing a range of information search and retrieval options based on fit-for-purpose content indexing.

In addition to the above, the following functional system requirements have been also considered⁶⁶:

- When a visitor enters the FarmBook platform, they will have access to a search bar with a linked results page containing filters to look for specific information, as well as sector and cross-sectoral, theme-related overview pages which allow the visitor to explore information more broadly.
- When a visitor enters the FarmBook platform, they will be able to search for specific information via the search bar and search filters where the format of the output is available.
- When a visitor enters the FarmBook platform, they will be able to search for information on, e.g., “forest management” by entering this in the search bar and subsequently filter the output per sector or cross-sectoral theme.

Figure 21 below shows the search bar on the homepage. There is the option to define whether the search should include every available category or is narrowed to one of the six top-level categories of primary interest to the user. To improve the user experience, these six categories are also displayed as tabs under the search bar with a representative image for each one.

⁶³ Task 1.3: “Learning from how the MA data is currently stored in KRs”.

⁶⁴ Task 2.2: “Develop detailed understanding of the end-user information needs and barriers (through end-user journeys) per archetype”.

⁶⁵ Task 3.1: “Evaluation and selection of data sets and knowledge objects”

⁶⁶ These requirements have been reported in Deliverable 4.1 (“Product Requirements Document”) (Van der Cruyssen et al., 2021).

Figure 21 – The FarmBook platform’s search bar and content categories

After submitting the search query, a view of the available results is returned as shown in Figure 22 below. The total number of available results displays some options that the users can choose from to modify the search results based on their needs. As an example, a user can sort the results based on the relevance, alphabetically, and according to time the content was uploaded. Furthermore, the results can be filtered by selecting the type of the content that a user needs, meaning Knowledge Objects themselves vs. the “Community” or “Expert” pages. In addition, the user can select multiple topics, subtopics, languages, and locations that the displayed items are related to.

Figure 22 - FarmBook search results and available filters

8 Conclusions and discussion

The work implemented in **Task 4.3** (“FarmBook Data Repository Development”) has involved a wide range of activities requiring various kinds of expertise coming from the partners. First and foremost, the work done in the context of the specific task has been of a technical nature given the task’s focus on the digital repository setup and the FarmBook digital platform’s search engine development. Apart from that, there has also been a considerable amount of work done at the conceptual level with respect to the definition of the metadata used for the Knowledge Object annotation and the revision and finalisation of the model of agriculture- and forestry-related subjects. The onboarding of Knowledge Objects to the repository of the FarmBook’s platform has taken place as part of a process launched from the assembly of an annotation team and its training. Both the repository and the search engine constitute integral components of the EUREKA FarmBook’s platform, and the results of the work for their setup and development has been input to the development of the whole FarmBook platform system (i.e., input to the work in **Task 4.4**). The work in EUREKA has paved the way towards practices enabling the adherence to the FAIR data principles, in the context of agriculture. It has laid the foundations for a FAIRer management of agriculture- and forestry-related digital content and information, enabling broader and more rapid knowledge sharing.

At the time this report was drafted, a total number of 880 Knowledge Objects (from 12 MA projects⁶⁷) had been ingested into the EUREKA FarmBook’s repository and were available to the users of the pilot version of the platform developed in EUREKA (<https://www.eufarmbook.eu/>). The attraction of interest of MA projects will continue for a six-month period after the completion of EUREKA as part of targeted actions

⁶⁷ This number of projects includes seven of the Thematic Network projects considered in EURAKNOS for the needs of development of the prototype version of the platform (i.e., the prototype e-KRP).

involving the participation of key partner organisations (e.g., UGent and AUA). This way, a smooth launch of the work of the follow-up project (i.e., the EU-FarmBook project funded under the HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-24 topic) will be achieved. Similarly, the content in the digital repository will be curated for the same period till the follow-up project launches its activities by building upon the work done in EUREKA. The technical work for the repository's setup and the search engine's development is legacy work to be furthered in the follow-up project. The choices that have been made regarding the digital repository and search engine technologies have been based on broadly acknowledged and tested solutions supported by vibrant communities of software engineers. Yet, given the time frame of the EU FarmBook project (it will have a seven-year duration), a review of the technology choices in EUREKA will have to be undertaken by keeping an eye to the future and building upon solutions having the capacity to endure for such a long period.

9 Acknowledgements

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⁶⁸ The roles/contribution of these partner organisations in the activities of Task 4.3 are described in the introductory section of the report.

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11 Annex I: Lists of predefined EUREKA metadata values

11.1 List of values for the “Subject” metadata property

When annotating a Knowledge Object with metadata in order to be ingested into the FarmBook’s digital repository, one of the properties to which values need to be assigned is the “Subject” metadata property. In that case, the annotators (or the platform users using the upload form for the supply of content to the FarmBook) had to select and provide the subject(s) of a Knowledge Object at two levels/steps, namely: (i) an initial level where one or more of the broad EUREKA subject/topic categories (i.e., “Crop farming”, “Livestock”, “Forestry”, “Environment”, “Society”, and “Economics”) had to be selected as value(s); and (ii) a second level, where one or more subject/topic categories from the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy had to be selected (based on the subject selections made at the previous step). Table 23 below presents the first-level subjects of the EUREKA FarmBook’s subject model and the EIP-AGRI subject/topic categories (i.e., macro-categories) associated with each of first-level subjects. The definitions of the first-level subjects and the EIP-AGRI macro-categories (developed as part of the work done on the fine-tuning of the subject model) are shown below.

Table 23 – First-level and second-level subjects of the EUREKA FarmBook’s model of agriculture- and forestry-related subjects and their alignment

Crop farming	Livestock	Forestry	Environment	Society	Economics
Biomass production	Biomass production	Biomass production	Biomass production	Biomass production	Biomass production
Agro-ecology	Aquaculture	Agro-ecology	Aquaculture	Agro-ecology	Aquaculture
Organic farming	Agro-ecology	Digitalisation	Agro-ecology	Organic farming	Agro-ecology
Digitalisation	Organic farming	Farm diversification/ new business models	Organic farming	Digitalisation	Organic farming
Farm diversification/new business models	Digitalisation	Competitiveness	Digitalisation	Farm diversification/ new business models	Digitalisation
Competitiveness	Farm diversification/new business models	AKIS	Farm diversification/ new business models	Competitiveness	Farm diversification/ new business models
Crop rotation/crop diversification	Competitiveness	Farming equipment and machinery	Competitiveness	AKIS	Competitiveness
AKIS	AKIS	Landscape/land management	Crop rotation/crop diversification	Animal husbandry and welfare	Crop rotation/crop diversification
Farming equipment and machinery	Farming equipment and machinery	Pest/disease control	AKIS	Plant production and horticulture	AKIS
Plant production and horticulture	Animal husbandry and welfare	Soil management/ functionality	Animal husbandry and welfare	Landscape/land management	Farming equipment and machinery
Pest/disease control	Plant production and horticulture	Genetic resource	Plant production and horticulture	Pest/disease control	Animal husbandry and welfare
Fertilisation and nutrients management	Pest disease/control	Energy management	Landscape/land management	Soil management/ functionality	Plant production and horticulture
Soil management/ functionality	Genetic resource	Farming/forestry competitiveness	Pest/disease control	Genetic resource	Landscape/land management
Genetic resource	Energy management	Biodiversity and nature management	Fertilisation and nutrients management	Energy management	Pest/disease control
Energy management	Supply chain, marketing & consumption	Waste, by-products & residues management	Soil management/ functionality	Supply chain, marketing & consumption	Fertilisation and nutrients management
Supply chain, marketing & consumption	Farming/forestry competitiveness	Climate and climate change, air	Genetic resource	Farming/forestry competitiveness	Soil management/ functionality

Farming/forestry competitiveness	Food quality processing & nutrition		Energy management	Food quality processing & nutrition	Genetic resource
Food quality processing & nutrition	Biodiversity and nature management		Supply chain, marketing & consumption	Biodiversity and nature management	Energy management
Biodiversity and nature management	Waste, by-products & residues management		Farming/forestry competitiveness	Waste, by-products & residues management	Supply chain, marketing & consumption
Waste, by-products & residues management	Climate and climate change, air		Food quality processing & nutrition	Climate and climate change, air	Farming/forestry competitiveness
Climate and climate change, air			Biodiversity and nature management		Food quality processing & nutrition
			Waste, by-products & residues management		Waste, by-products & residues management
		Climate and climate change, air		Climate and climate change, air	

11.1.1 Definitions of first-level subjects

Crop farming → The cultivation of plants for food, animal feed, or other commercial use.

Livestock → The activity of raising domesticated animals in an agricultural setting to produce labour and commodities such as meat, eggs, milk, fur, leather, and wool.⁶⁹

Forestry → Managing and using trees, forests, and their associated resources for human benefit.

Environment → The natural environment encompasses all living and non-living things occurring naturally, meaning in this case not artificial.⁷⁰

Society → People in general thought of as living together in organized communities with shared laws, traditions, and values.⁷¹

Economics → Economics focuses on the actions of human beings, based on assumptions that humans act with rational behaviour, seeking the most optimal level of benefit or utility. The building blocks of economics are the studies of labour and trade. Since there are many possible applications of human labour and many different ways to acquire resources, it is the task of economics to determine which methods yield the best results.⁷²

11.1.2 Definitions of second-level subjects (EIP- Definitions of EIP-AGRI macro-categories)

Biomass production → Production of the biodegradable fraction of products, waste, and residues from biological origin - from agriculture (including vegetal and animal substances), forestry and aquaculture, as well as the biodegradable fraction of industrial and municipal waste⁷³.

⁶⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Livestock>

⁷⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Natural_environment

⁷¹ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/society>

⁷² <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/e/economics.asp>

⁷³ https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/bioeconomy/topic/biomass_en#agriculture

Aquaculture → Aquaculture is the farming of aquatic organisms, including fish, molluscs, crustaceans and aquatic plants⁷⁴.

Agro-ecology → Agroecology is a holistic and integrated approach that simultaneously applies ecological and social concepts and principles to the design and management of sustainable agriculture and food systems⁷⁵.

Organic farming → Organic farming/agriculture is a production system that sustains the health of soils, ecosystems, and people. It relies on ecological processes, biodiversity and cycles adapted to local conditions, rather than the use of inputs with adverse effects⁷⁶.

Digitalisation → Use of technology to convert precise data into actionable knowledge to drive and support complex decision-making on-farm and along the value chain⁷⁷.

Farm diversification/new business models → Farm diversification refers to the trend towards gaining income from diverse activities (e.g., agri-tourism, processing of farm products)⁷⁸.

Competitiveness → Competitiveness is the ability of the farm to compete and be successful.

Crop rotation/crop diversification → Crop rotation is growing a different crop on a given land area every growing/planting cycle and season⁷⁹. Crop diversification refers to the addition of new crops or cropping systems to agricultural production on a particular farm taking into account the different returns from value-added crops with complementary marketing opportunities⁸⁰.

AKIS → The term Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) is used to describe the whole knowledge exchange system: the ways people and organisations interact within a country or a region. AKIS can include farming practice, businesses, authorities, research, etc. and can vary a lot, depending on the country or sector⁸¹.

Farming equipment and machinery → All machines and tools that are used in the production, harvesting, transport and storage of farm products.

Animal husbandry and welfare → The branch of agriculture concerned with the production, management, and breeding of animals.

Plant production and horticulture → Plant production refers to the cultivation of plants for food, feed, fiber, medicinal and cosmetic purposes. Horticulture is defined as that branch of agriculture concerned with growing plants that are used by people for food, for medicinal purposes, and for aesthetic gratification.

⁷⁴ <https://www.fao.org/3/x6941e/x6941e04.htm>

⁷⁵ <https://www.fao.org/agroecology/home/en/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.ifoam.bio/why-organic/organic-landmarks/definition-organic>

⁷⁷ Adapted from <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/digital-technology>

⁷⁸ Adapted from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Farm_typology

⁷⁹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/crop-rotation>

⁸⁰ <https://www.ctc-n.org/technologies/crop-diversification-and-new-varieties>

⁸¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/publications/eip-agri-brochure-agricultural-knowledge-and>

Landscape/land management → Land management concerns all operations, practices and treatments used to protect the land and enhance the goods and services provided by the ecosystem that the land is part of.

Pest/disease control → Any measures, practices and strategies applied to prevent the appearance or spread of pests and diseases in plant production or to limit their impact on plant growth, crop yield and product quality.

Fertilisation and nutrients management → Careful management, monitoring and amending of soil fertility to meet crops' needs and to maintain environmental quality.

Soil management/functionality → Management of soil by focusing on differences in soil types and soil characteristics to define specific interventions that are aimed to enhance the soil health and quality for the selected land use.

Genetic resource → Any genetic material of plant and animal origin of actual or potential value for food and agriculture.

Energy management → All practices and measures applied for the efficient and responsible use of energy resources in agricultural production systems.

Supply chain, marketing, and consumption → The full chain of activities and network among the actors for the preparation of a product or service starting from the raw material production till the marketing and consumption.

Farm/forestry competitiveness and diversification → Improvement of the competitiveness of the agriculture and forestry sectors, as well as the quality of life in rural areas and encouragement of diversification of economic activities.

Food quality/processing and nutrition → All aspects concerned with processing, preparing, preserving, and distributing foods and beverages, their quality characteristics and nutritional value.

Biodiversity and nature management → Management and sustainable development of nature and conservation of diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems.

Waste, by-products, and residues management → Managing waste in an environmentally sound manner and making use of the secondary materials they contain.

Climate and climate change → Climate is the average weather in a given area over a longer period of time. A description of a climate includes information on, e.g. the average temperature in different seasons, rainfall, and sunshine. Also, a description of the (chance of) extremes is often included.⁸²

Climate change is a long-term change in the average weather patterns that have come to define Earth's local, regional and global climates.

⁸² <https://www.climateurope.eu/what-is-climate-and-climate-change/>

11.2 List of values for the “Geographic location(s)” metadata property

Åland Islands, Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Faroe Islands, Finland, France, Germany, Gibraltar, Greece, Guernsey, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Isle of Man, Italy, Jan Mayen, Jersey, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Moldova, Monaco, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Republic of Northern Macedonia, Romania, Russia, San Marino, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Svalbard, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom, and Vatican City.

11.3 List of values for the “Language(s)” metadata property

Bulgarian, Croatian, Czech, Danish, Dutch, English, Estonian, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Irish, Italian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Maltese, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Slovak, Slovenian, Spanish, and Swedish.

11.4 List of values for the “Intended purpose” metadata property

Access to data, communication, dissemination, education/training, data storage/processing, monitoring, modelling, evaluation, decision-making support, prediction/forecasting, and experimentation.

11.5 List of values for the “Type” metadata property

11.5.1 Types of documents

Article in conference proceedings → A research paper presented in a conference by one (or more) of its authors; after the end of the conference, the paper is published in the conference proceedings (i.e. an edited volume with all the papers presented in the conference).

Book → A digital version of a book.

Booklet → A small book or group of pages.

Brochure → A digital document (of limited size in terms of its number of pages) containing pictures and information on a product or a company (or, in our case, a Multi-Actor Project).

Chapter in edited volume → A document presenting research work, which has been included in a book (edited volume) containing chapters from various contributors. This edited volume usually addresses a specific research topic. An example of a chapter in an edited volume is provided [here](#).

Deliverable report → A document used to report the work done in a project as part of one, or more, tasks, which has led to some results.

Factsheet → A document containing detailed information, for the public, about a product or service.

Flyer → A form of paper-based advertisement intended for wide distribution and typically distributed or posted in a public place, handed out to individuals or sent through the mail. This document type is very close to the “brochure” type.

Handbook → A book including instructions on how to use something or information about a particular subject.

Guide → A book that gives the most important information about a particular subject.

Journal article → A piece of writing documenting the process and results of a research effort, which is published in a scientific journal. An example of a journal article is available [here](#).

Manual → A book giving instructions or information.

Milestone report → A document used to report the work undertaken in a research project, which has resulted in the achievement of a milestone (milestone = a significant stage or event in a development process).

Newsletter → A short official statement or broadcast summary of news issued periodically to the members of a society or other organisation.

Policy brief → A policy brief is a concise summary of a particular issue, the policy options to deal with it, and some recommendations on the best option. It is aimed at government policymakers and others who are interested in formulating or influencing policies.

Practice abstract → A document used to disseminate the results of the project in a concise and understandable way to the practitioners. An example of a practice abstract is available [here](#).

Press release → A press release is an official statement delivered to members of the news media for the purpose of providing information, an official statement, or making an announcement. Press releases can be delivered to members of the media physically on paper and electronically.

Review document → A document used with the aim to provide a review of some piece of work (review = a formal assessment of something with the intention of instituting change if necessary).

Report/paper → A document containing an account given on a particular matter, after thorough investigation or consideration, by a person or body. The information presented is usually supported by strong evidence.

Technical/technology article → This is usually a document presenting a technical topic, and typically the article drills down into some low-level of detail.

Technical information/specifications card → A document presenting a list of technical information about a product or service by having the layout of a “card”.

Thesis → A piece of writing involving original study of a subject, esp. for a college or university degree.

Tutorial → A document showcasing how to use a product or service in a series of steps.

11.5.2 Types of slideshow presentations

Educational/training presentation → A presentation developed and used for educational/training purposes in an educational/ training event/session.

Guide → A type of presentation providing information and/or instructions to help a person understand or execute something.

Informative presentation → This type of presentation is used to present specific information to specific audiences for specific goals or functions. Informative presentations are often analytical or involve the

rational analysis of information. Sometimes they simply “report the facts” with no analysis at all, but still need to communicate the information in a clear and concise format.

Tutorial (similar to guide) → A presentation type providing practical information about a specific subject.

Motivational presentation → A presentation aiming to provide its audience with the incentive to do something specific (e.g. make a decision, take an action, etc.).

Decision-making presentation → A presentation developed and used with the aim to facilitate decision-making purposes. In this case, however, decision-making is facilitated by the display and analysis of facts/data/results. It does not draw on the emotional factor as in the case of motivational presentations.

Problem-solving presentation

A presentation created and used with the aim to provide help on how to solve a problem.

11.5.3 Types of videos

Vlog → A record of someone’s thoughts, opinions, or experiences that he/she films and publishes on the internet.

Webinar → The video recording of a seminar session that has taken place online (i.e. a webinar).

Guide → A video that gives you the most important information about a particular subject. For instance: a travel guide available as a video or a wine guide available as a video.

Event capturing video → A video recording of an event. As an example, case, we may refer to the video recording of the consortium meeting of a project (e.g., the video available at <https://www.youtube.com/...=EURAKNOSProject>).

Tutorial/how-to video → A video showing how to use or do something in a series of easy stages.

Presentation/live talk capturing video → A video recording of a discussion of two or more people (e.g., the video available at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uqeqnE7CLr8&ab_channel=OxfordUnion).

Interview video → A video recording of an interview event (e.g., the video available at **Error! Hyperlink reference not valid.**)

Product/feature review video → A video presenting the basic features of an object/product/device (e.g., the video available at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OoY7zp8GkLI&ab_channel=MarquesBrownle).

Documentary video → A video presenting facts and information about a subject. For instance, a documentary video on animal communication (e.g., the video available at <https://www.youtube.com/...=BestDocumentary>).

Testimonial → A video presenting a person's statement extolling the virtue of a product/service or something else (e.g., the video available at <https://www.youtube.com/...=EpicProductions%2CLLC>).

Question-and-answer video → A video where a person responds to a number of questions posed by a live audience or being made available in another way (e.g., the video available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ciNG2WdfJjc>).

Case study → A video providing detailed information about the development of a person, group, or thing, especially in order to show general principles (e.g., the video available at <https://www.youtube.com/...=NurtureDigital>).

Simulation video → A video presenting a model of a real activity or phenomenon, created for training purposes or to solve a problem (e.g., the video available at <https://www.youtube.com/...=AnselmoLaManna>).

Educational/training video → A video that has been developed for educational/training purposes (e.g., the video available at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dCOojwkWO8c&ab_channel=BlueSkyFilm%26Media).

11.5.4 Types of audios

Educational/training podcast → An audio object/podcast that has been developed and used for educational/training purposes in the context of an educational/training event/session.

Event capturing podcast → An audio object/podcast created with the aim to record an event. It is an audio documentary of this event.

Interview → This type of audio object/podcast is to provide the recorded interview of some person.

Solo podcast → This is a common type of audio object/podcast and it is often used by people who have expertise in a certain area and want to share with an audience.

Tutorial/guide → An audio object/podcast providing instructions on how to use a product, or undertake a process, in a series of easy stages.

Commentary → An audio object/podcast containing opinions or explanations of an event or situation.

Panel discussion → An audio object/podcast recording a group of people gathered together to discuss a topic in the presence of an audience. Panels usually include a moderator who coordinates the discussion and sometimes elicits audience questions, with the goal of being informative and entertaining.

Question-and-answer podcast → An audio object/podcast used to record the responses of an expert to the questions asked by another person who is in charge of the Q&A session.

On-demand seminar → An audio object/podcast that has been created with the purpose to record a seminar/training session. The recorded session is then available to any interested individual on his/her demand.

Audio magazine → A podcast that incorporates a range of different thematic units as a magazine does.

11.5.5 Types of images

Chart/graph → A chart is a sheet providing information in tabular form. Chart examples are available [here](#). A graph is a diagram (e.g., a series of one or more points, lines, line segments, curves, or areas) representing the variation of a variable in comparison to one or more other variables. Graph examples are available [here](#).

Static figure/image → A display of information through various illustration means (e.g., colours, lines, borders, arrows, photographs) that does not employ any motion-related aspects. Examples are available [here](#).

Interactive figure/image → A figure or image that makes use of motion-related aspects. An example of interactive figures/images are the [animated gifs](#).

Infographic → A collection of imagery, charts, and minimal text providing an easy-to-understand overview of a topic. Infographic examples are available [here](#).

Static map → A representation usually on a flat surface of the whole or a part of an area/a diagram or other visual representation that shows the relative position of the parts of something. Examples of static are available [here](#).

Interactive map → Interactive map examples are available [here](#).

11.5.6 Types of datasets

Auditory data → An auditory dataset contains audio-related data.

Crop-related data → Crop-related datasets contain values associated with variables of interest to the growing of crops and crop production.

Geospatial data → According to the Cambridge online dictionary⁸³, the term “geospatial” is used to denote data and information identifying where particular features are on the earth's surface, such as oceans and mountains. Thus, a set of geospatial data contains records that have locational information tied to them such as geographic data in the form of coordinates, address, city, or ZIP code.

Graph-related data → The term “graph-related data” is used to denote any dataset available in the format of a graph. There may be various sources from which a graph-based dataset may have originated from. Well known examples of such datasets are Knowledge Graphs. An example of a Knowledge Graph can be found [here](#).

Imagery data → A dataset that has images as its records. These images may show, for instance, plants infected by various diseases, which can be used for precision crop protection applications.

Input-related data → A dataset of this type contains data in various formats, which relate to the inputs applied to a crop.

Network-related data → This dataset type has similarities with the graph-related dataset type given the fact that from a mathematical perspective graphs and networks are defined upon similar theoretical foundations. Network-based data may convey information about network structures such as relationships and interactions among stakeholders in a value chain.

Temporal data → Sets of temporal data contain data that represents a state in time. Temporal data is collected and utilised for purposes such as the analysis of weather patterns and other environmental variables, monitoring traffic conditions, studying demographic trends, etc. Data relating to this type may be collected manually, by using sensors, or generated from simulation models.

Textual data → Textual data originate from plain text. It is an unstructured type of data having the potential to reveal useful insights relating to various variables of interest. Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a continuously growing research field in the domain of computational linguistics that involves research in models and techniques used to process textual data.

Video data → Video data relates to data that can be potentially extracted or relating to video recordings.

⁸³ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/>

Weather/climate data → In the case of this type of datasets, we are dealing with data relating to the weather and climatic conditions affecting a geographic region. This data may become available from weather stations and satellites.

Yield-related data → This type of dataset contains data about the yield of a crop. Historical yield-related data may be potentially used (together with data of other types) to proceed to yield estimations. This type of data has a temporal dimension.

11.5.7 Types of software applications

AI software → This type relates to software applications deploying Artificial Intelligence algorithms/models. As an example, we may refer to chatbots or Q&A tools the use of which allows the user to verbally pose queries (e.g., Amazon Alexa).

Business software → This type relates to software developed to support various business processes. As an example, we may refer to software applications used for storing and information about the customers of a business. This type of software is usually developed by software development vendors and made available through license purchase.

Data repository/database → This software application type relates to systems used to store information/data of various types of importance to an organisation. SQL and NoSQL systems are two prominent paradigms of such applications.

Data analysis software → Software applications used for performing various types of data analysis. WEKA⁸⁴ is a well-known data analysis application.

Decision support tool → A Decision Support Tool or Decision Support System is an information system used with the aim to support decision-making processes. This type of software applications serve the management, operations and planning levels of an organisation and help people make decisions with regard to problems that may be rapidly changing and that cannot be easily specified in advance.

Educational/training software → Software applications that have been specifically developed for education and training purposes.

Farm Management Information System (FMIS) → The acronym FMIS stands for Farm Management Information System. A Farm Management Information System is a management information system designed to assist agricultural farmers to perform various tasks ranging from operational planning, implementation and documentation for assessment of performed field work.⁸⁵

Game → The term game is used here to refer to a video game developed with the aim to support training and educational purposes. This kind of educational/training video games are termed as serious games. The reason for not including this type into the educational/training software application category is because of their prominent role in educational/training contexts. A serious game is a game designed for a primary purpose other than pure entertainment.⁸⁶

⁸⁴ <https://www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/ml/weka/>

⁸⁵ Burlacu, G., Costa, R., Sarraipa, J., Jardim - Golcalves, R. and Popescu, D. (2014). A Conceptual Model of Farm Management Information System for Decision Support. In Doctoral Conference on Computing, Electrical and Industrial Systems (pp. 47-54). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

⁸⁶ Djaouti, D., Alvarez, J. and Jessel, J.P. (2011). Classifying serious games: the G/P/S model. In Handbook of research on improving learning and motivation through educational games: Multidisciplinary approaches (pp. 118-136). IGI Global.

Scientific software → This type includes software applications developed with the aim to support scientific purposes. As an example, we may refer to [bioinformatics software](#).

Simulation → A simulation is a software application developed with aim to deliver an approximate imitation of the operation of a process or system that represents its operation over time⁸⁷.

⁸⁷ Banks, J. (2005). Discrete event system simulation. Pearson Education India.

12 Annex II: Definitions proposed for the EIP-AGRI macro-categories and their semantic networks

Table 24 below presents the definitions that have been proposed for each topic category in the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy as part of the process of revising and finalising the EUREKA FarmBook’s subject model.

Table 24 - Agricultural topic categories in the EIP-AGRI’s taxonomy and the definitions proposed as part of the process of revising and finalizing the EUREKA FarmBook’s subject model

EIP-AGRI topic category	Definition
Farming equipment and machinery	All machines and tools that are used in the production, harvesting, transport and storage of farm products.
Animal husbandry and welfare	The branch of agriculture concerned with the production, management, and breeding of animals.
Plant production and horticulture	Plant production refers to the cultivation of plants for food, feed, fiber, medicinal and cosmetic purposes. Horticulture is defined as that branch of agriculture concerned with growing plants that are used by people for food, for medicinal purposes, and for aesthetic gratification.
Landscape/land management	Land management is concerned with all the operations, practices and treatments used to protect the land and enhance the goods and services provided by the ecosystem that the land is part of.
Pest/disease control	Any measures, practices and strategies applied to prevent the appearance or spread of pests and diseases in plant production or to limit their impact on plant growth, crop yield and product quality.
Fertilisation and nutrients management	Careful management, monitoring and amending of soil fertility to meet crop needs and maintain environmental quality.
Soil management/functionality	Management of soil by focusing on differences in soil types and soil characteristics to define specific interventions that are aimed to enhance the soil health and quality for the selected land use.
Genetic resource	Any genetic material of plant and animal origin of actual or potential value for food and agriculture.
Forestry	Managing and using trees, forests, and their associated resources for human benefit.
Energy management	All practices and measures applied for the efficient and responsible use of energy resources in agricultural production systems.
Supply chain, management, and consumption	The full chain of activities and network among the actors for the preparation of a product or service starting from the raw material production till the marketing and consumption.
Farming/forestry competitiveness	Improvement of the competitiveness of the agriculture and forestry sectors, as well as the quality of life in rural areas.
Food quality/processing and nutrition	All aspects concerned with processing, preparing, preserving, and distributing foods and beverages, their quality characteristics and nutritional value.
Biodiversity and nature management	Management and sustainable development of nature and conservation of diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems.
Waste, by-products, and residues management	Managing waste in an environmentally sound manner and making use of the secondary materials they contain.
Climate and climate change	Climate change is a long-term change in the average weather patterns that have come to define Earth’s local, regional, and global climates.

Biomass production	Production of the biodegradable fraction of products, waste, and residues from biological origin - from agriculture (including vegetal and animal substances), forestry and aquaculture, as well as the biodegradable fraction of industrial and municipal waste.
Aquaculture	Aquaculture is the farming of aquatic organisms in both coastal and inland areas involving interventions in the rearing process to enhance production.
Agro-ecology	Agroecology is a holistic and integrated approach that simultaneously applies ecological and social concepts and principles to the design and management of sustainable agriculture and food systems.
Organic farming	Organic Agriculture is a production system that sustains the health of soils, ecosystems, and people. It relies on ecological processes, biodiversity and cycles adapted to local conditions, rather than the use of inputs with adverse effects.
Digitalisation	The creation and practical use of digital or computerised devices, methods, systems, etc. to drive and support complex decision-making on-farm and along the value chain.
Farm diversification/new business models	Development of new income-earning activities other than farm work (e.g., agri-tourism, processing of farm products) directly related to the holding or having an economic impact on the holding.
Competitiveness	The ability of the farm to compete and be successful.
Crop rotation/crop diversification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop rotation is growing a different crop on a given land area every growing/planting cycle and season. • Crop diversification refers to the addition of new crops or cropping systems to agricultural production on a particular farm considering the different returns from value-added crops with complementary marketing opportunities.
AKIS	The term Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) is used to describe the whole knowledge exchange system; the ways people and organisations interact within a country or a region. AKIS can include farming practices, businesses, authorities, research, etc. and can vary a lot, depending on the country or sector.

Table 25 below presents the AGROVOC concepts, agricultural sectors, and cross-sectoral themes that have been associated with each agricultural topic category in the EIP-AGRI taxonomy as part of the creation of the EIP-AGRI topic category’s semantic network.

Table 25 - AGROVOC concepts, agricultural sectors, and cross-sectoral themes associated with each agricultural topic category in the EIP-AGRI taxonomy

EIP-AGRI topic category	AGROVOC concepts with a broader scope	AGROVOC concepts with a narrower scope	AGROVOC concepts with a similar scope	Crop Farming	Livestock	Forestry	Environment	Society	Economics

Farming equipment and machinery	Farm equipment	Animal husbandry equipment; Cultivation equipment; Fertilizer equipment; Hand tools; Irrigation equipment; Harvesters	Digital technology	X	X	X			X
Animal husbandry and welfare	Agricultural practices	Animal husbandry methods; apiculture; organic husbandry; poultry farming; animal breeding; insect farming; animal housing; animal health	Animal welfare		X		X	X	X
Plant production and horticulture	Crop production; Agricultural production	Cultivation; plant propagation; arboriculture; floriculture; fruit growing; hop growing; vegetable growing; orchards; feed crops; medicinal plants; greenhouse crops	-	X		X	X	X	X

Landscape/land management	Natural resources management	Dryland management; earthmoving; integrated land management; land clearing; land concentration; land conservation; land rent; land use; pastoral lands; sustainable land management	Environmental restoration; land dispute; land fragmentation			X	X	X	X
Pest/disease control	Plant protection; pest management; disease management	Bird control; insect control; mite control; mollusc control; nematode control; parasite control; rodent control; weed control; biological control; chemical control; cultural methods; integrated pest management; phytosanitary measures	Plant breeding; disease control; pest control; postharvest control	X	X	X	X	X	X
Fertilisation and nutrients management	Farming systems; plant nutrition; nutrient cycles	Integrated plant nutrient management; site-specific nutrient management; soil fertility; soil quality; green manures; animal manures; composting	Precision agriculture; soil management	X			X		X

Soil management/ functionality	Soil fertility; soil quality; nutrient management	Drainage; salinity control; site preparation; soil conservation; soil treatment; tillage; soil erosion; soil organic matter; irrigation; soil management; soil improvement; seedbed preparation; integrated land management; soil analysis; soil fertility; soil amendments; soil water balance; soil biology	Natural resources management; biodiversity	X		X	X	X	X
Genetic resource	Biological resources	Animal genetic resources; DNA libraries; forest genetic resources; gene banks; gene pools; germplasm; plant genetic resources; transcriptome; varieties; micro- organisms; invertebrates; biodiversity; wildlife	Biotechnology; climate change	X	X	X	X	X	X

Forestry	-	Forestry operations; silviculture; forest management; forest protection; forestry operations; forest trees; tree classes	-				X			
Energy management	Resource management	Energy demand; energy conservation; renewable energy; bioenergy	Energy policies	X						
Supply chain, marketing, and consumption	Production economics; economic behavior	Feed supply chains; food supply chains; domestic consumption; feed consumption; food consumption; marketing; consumers	-	X	X			X	X	X
Farming/forestry competitiveness	Economic development; rural development	Direct marketing; agrotourism	Food production; forestry production	X						
Food quality/processing and nutrition	Food safety; food security; nutrition	Nutritive value; processing; packaging; storage; transport; food quality; organic foods; food technology	-	X	X			X	X	X

Biodiversity and nature management	Biological resources; resource conservation	Abundance; agrobiodiversity; forest biodiversity; genetic diversity; natural heritage; species richness; biodiversity conservation; ecosystem conservation; landscape conservation	Cryptic species; habitat loss; river restoration	X	X	X	X	X	
Waste, by-products, and residues management	Resource management; environmental management; substances	Aerobic treatment; agricultural waste management; anaerobic treatment; composting; waste collection; waste reduction; waste treatment; waste utilization; antibiotic residues; drug residues; organic residues; pesticide residues	Waste treatment	X	X	X	X	X	X

Climate and climate change	Natural phenomena; environment	Arid climate; coastal climate; continental climate; dry subhumid climate; humid climate; hydroclimate; macroclimate; mediterranean climate; mesoclimate; microclimate; moist subhumid climate; monsoon climate; mountain climate; oceanic climate; palaeoclimate; global warming	Climate system; climate change adaptation; climate change mitigation	X	X	X	X	X	X
Biomass production	Biological production	-	Food security; soil functions	X	X	X	X	X	X

Farm diversification/new business models	Models	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X
Competitiveness	Entities	-	Farm income; farm indebtedness; financial situation; profitability; agricultural situation; costs; accounting	X	X	X	X	X	X
Crop rotation/crop diversification	Cropping systems	Ley farming	Leys, dry farming, shifting cultivation, catch cropping, fallow systems, sequential cropping	X			X		X
AKIS	Participation	-	Public participation; social participation	X	X	X	X	X	X

13 Annex III: EUREKA FarmBook repository’s FAIRness evaluation report

This Annex section provides the various sections of the report generated by the SATIFYD tool in respect to the evaluation of the EUREKA FarmBook digital repository’s FAIRness evaluation.

Figure 23 – Report generated by SATIFYD regarding the score of the evaluation of the “Findable” principle

Figure 24 - Report generated by SATIFYD regarding the score of the evaluation of the “Accessible” principle

Figure 25 - Report generated by SATIFYD regarding the score of the evaluation of the “Interoperable” principle

Figure 26 - Report generated by SATIFYD regarding the score of the evaluation of the “Reusable” principle

14 Annex IV: EUREKA FarmBook code documentation

This Annex section provides code instances from various parts that were used for uploading single or batches of knowledge objects into the data repository of EUREKA FarmBook. The code repository will be available in Zenodo for further use and analysis.

```
const log = (type: any) => console.log.bind(console, type);
return <div onScroll={onScroll} className="App">
  <div className="c-header">
    <div className="c-header__container u-container">
      <h1 className="c-header__title">
        EUREKA Knowledge Object Upload Form
      </h1>

      <p className="c-header__description">
        Single object upload form for the EUREKA Farmbook.
        For automated large scale uploads of already structured metadata,
        please contact us on the #eureka-development slack channel.
      </p>
    </div>
  </div>

  <div className="u-container">
    <Snackbar open={open} autoHideDuration={8000}
onClose={handleClose}>
      <Alert onClose={handleClose} severity="success">
        Upload was succesful. To speed up potential similar
        uploads the form is not cleared. Press 'Clear fields' to start from scratch.
      </Alert>
    </Snackbar>

    <Form
      schema={schema}
      formData={formData}
      className=""
      uiSchema={uiSchema}
      widgets={customWidgets}
      onSubmit={submitForm}
      onError={log("errors")}
      showErrorList={false}
      validate={validate}
      transformErrors={transformErrors}
      liveValidate />

    <div className='u-container' style={{ textAlign: "center",
paddingBottom: "100px", marginTop: "-100px" }}>
    <p>Once you have filled all required fields correctly and submit, you will
have the option to download a copy of the metadata file in CSV format. This
can be used as a template for larger batch uploads of knowledge objects. Get
in touch with us at eufarmbook@ugent.be if you are interested in this
option!</p>

    <CSVLink
      className="u-container MuiButtonBase-root MuiButton-
root MuiButton-contained MuiButton-containedPrimary"
```



```
        data={ csvArr }
        target="_blank"
        style={{width: "200px"}}
        separator={";"}
      >
        Download in CSV
      </CSVLink>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>;
```

Figure 27 – ReactJS code used to define the main structure of the uploading form of a single knowledge object

```
const headers = [
  "Id",
  "dc.title",
  "creativework.description",
  "dcterms.creator",
  "creativework.keywords",
  "creativework.inLanguage",
  "creativework.contentLocation",
  "dcterms.format",
  "creativework.dateCreated",
  "knowledgeobject.dateExtracted",
  "creativework.potentialAction",
  "creativework.url",
  "knowledgeobject.filetype",
  "dcterms.subject",
  "dcterms.type",
  "knowledgeobject.macroCategory",
  "creativework.license",
  "knowledgeobject.project.acronym",
  "knowledgeobject.project.name",
  "knowledgeobject.project.url",
];

const data = [
  "1",
  formData['Title'],
  formData['Description'],
  formData['Creators'] ? formData['Creators'] : "n.a.",
  formData['Keywords'] ? formData['Keywords'] : "n.a.",
  formData['Languages'] ? formData['Languages'] : "n.a.",
  formData['GeographicalLocations'] ?
formData['GeographicalLocations'] : "n.a.",
  "n.a.",
  formData['KnowledgeObjectDate'].ExactDate.date ?
formData['KnowledgeObjectDate'].ExactDate.date : "n.a.",
  "n.a.",
  formData['IntendedPurpose']['What is the intended purpose of
the object?'] ? formData['IntendedPurpose']['What is the intended purpose of
the object?'] : "n.a.",
  formData['KnowledgeObjectLocation']['Knowledge Object URL'] ?
formData['KnowledgeObjectLocation']['Knowledge Object URL'] : "n.a.",
  categoryName,
```



```

        formData['SubjectOne'] ? formData['SubjectOne'] : "n.a.",
        types,
        formData['SubjectTwo:'] ? formData['SubjectTwo:'] : "n.a.",
        formData['License']['Under which license will the knowledge
object be made available?'],
        formData['ProjectAcronym'],
        formData['ProjectName'],
        formData['ProjectURL']
    ];

```

Figure 28 – Definition of the required headers and of the format that the uploaded knowledge object will have

```

    let csv = headers.join(';') + '\n';
    let row = "";
    for (let i = 0; i <= data.length - 1; i += 1) {
        if (Array.isArray(data[i])) {
            let str = "";
            for (let j = 0; j <= data[i].length - 1; j +=1) {
                str += (j === data[i].length - 1) ? data[i][j] :
(data[i][j] + ';');
            }
            csvArr[1].push(str);
            row += '\"'+ str + '\"';
        } else {
            csvArr[1].push(data[i]);
            row += (i === data.length - 1) ? data[i] : (data[i] + ';');
        }
    }
    csv += (row+'\n');
    let csvContent = new Blob([csv], { type: 'text/csv;charset=utf-8;'
});

    fileForm.append('file', csvContent);
    fetch('https://upload-prd.eufarmbook.eu/api/register', {
        method: 'POST',
        headers: {
            'Authorization': 'Basic
YWRtaW5AZXVmYXJtYm9vay5ldTpaKlJlTkVtd3N4eWJeMw==',
            'Cookie': 'JSESSIONID=A4DF302A506EE8B431F2A44F7C8817BB',
        },
        body: fileForm
    })
        .then(response => {
            if (response.ok) {
                window.scrollTo(0, 0)
                setOpen(true);
                setCsvArr(csvArr);
            } else {
                console.log("response not ok: " +
JSON.stringify(response));
            }
        })
        .catch(error => {
            console.log("error: " + JSON.stringify(error));
        });

```

```
}
```

Figure 29 – Creation of a csv object after uploading single knowledge object through the form and uploading of the created file through POST request to the dspace repository

```
/**
 *
 * @param file CSV file containing the knowledge objects to ingest.
 * @return Currently always returns a 200 status. Processing continues
 after response.
 * @throws IOException
 */
@PostMapping("/register")
public ResponseEntity register(@RequestParam("file") MultipartFile file)
    throws IOException, NoSuchMethodException,
    IllegalAccessException, InvocationTargetException {
    log.info("Started registration of knowledge objects for: {}",
file.getOriginalFilename());
    importPackagingService.registerRemoteKnowledgeObjects(file);
    log.info("Finished registration of knowledge objects for: {}",
file.getOriginalFilename());
    return ResponseEntity.ok().build();
}
```

Figure 30 – Function for initial registration of a knowledge object in the repository

```
public KnowledgeObject normalize(KnowledgeObject knowledgeObject)
    throws NoSuchMethodException, InvocationTargetException,
    IllegalAccessException {
    Map<String, String> optionalMetaData =
knowledgeObject.getOptionalMetaData();
    for(Field field : FieldsObject.class.getDeclaredFields()){
        String fieldString = field.getName();
        fieldString = StringUtils.capitalize(fieldString);
        Method method = FieldsObject.class.getMethod("get" + fieldString,
null);
        String mapKey = (String) method.invoke(fieldsObject, null);
        String metaDataValue = optionalMetaData.get(mapKey);
        if(metaDataValue == null ||
NOT_AVAILABLE.equals(metaDataValue.toLowerCase())){
            optionalMetaData.put(mapKey, NOT_AVAILABLE);
            continue;
        }
        Method standardizeMethod =
this.getClass().getDeclaredMethod("standardize" + fieldString, String.class);
        String value = (String) standardizeMethod.invoke(this,
metaDataValue);
        optionalMetaData.put(mapKey, value);
    }
    knowledgeObject.getOptionalMetaData().put(fieldsObject.getDateExtracted(),
createExtractedDate());
    return knowledgeObject;
}

private String normalize(String value){
```



```

        if(value == null){
            return value;
        }
        if(value.contains(",")){
            log.info("Value {} contains a comma, leading to ambiguous number
of entries.", value);
            return null;
        }
        String newValue = value.trim();
        newValue = newValue.toLowerCase();
        newValue = newValue.replaceAll("&", "and");
        return newValue;
    }

```

Figure 31 – Functions for normalizing the uploaded metadata of a knowledge object in the appropriate format to be ingested in the dspace repository

```

/**
 * Converts all supplied knowledge objects in CSV to the DSpace SAF
format.
 * Binary files should be present in the DSpace registration store.
 * @param file CSV containing knowledge objects and their local path
relative to the specified folder.
 * @param folderPath Folderpath path relative to the registration store
in which the files are stored.
 * @throws IOException Thrown when encountering issues with CSV parsing
or writing SAF structure.
 */
    public void registerLocalKnowledgeObjects(MultipartFile file, String
folderPath)
        throws IOException, NoSuchMethodException,
IllegalAccessException, InvocationTargetException {
        List<KnowledgeObject> knowledgeObjects = parseMetaCsv(file);
        String folderName = folderPath;

        for(KnowledgeObject knowledgeObject : knowledgeObjects){
            String fileName =
knowledgeObject.getOptionalMetaData().get("knowledgeobject.filepath");
            Path filePath =
Paths.get(dspaceConfig.getAssetFolder().toString(), folderPath, fileName);
            File koFile = filePath.toFile();
            knowledgeObject.setFileName(koFile.getName());
            knowledgeObject.setFilePath(koFile.toPath());

            knowledgeObject.getOptionalMetaData().remove("knowledgeobject.filepath");
        }
        for(KnowledgeObject knowledgeObject : knowledgeObjects) {
            String uuid = getUuid();
            registerToDspace(knowledgeObject, folderName, uuid);
        }
    }

/**
 * Converts all supplied knowledge objects in CSV to the DSpace SAF
format.
 * Files are downloaded from a remote location specified in the CSV
entries.

```

```

    * @param file CSV containing knowledge objects and their URL path.
    * @throws IOException Thrown when encountering issues with CSV parsing
    or writing SAF structure.
    */
    public void registerRemoteKnowledgeObjects(MultipartFile file)
        throws IOException, NoSuchMethodException,
        IllegalAccessException, InvocationTargetException {
        List<KnowledgeObject> knowledgeObjects = parseMetaDataCsv(file);
        for(KnowledgeObject knowledgeObject : knowledgeObjects){
            String uuid = getUuid();
            Path registrationFolderPath =
                createFolderPath(dspaceConfig.getAssetFolder(), uuid);
            knowledgeObject = downloadBitStream(knowledgeObject,
                registrationFolderPath);
            registerToDspace(knowledgeObject, uuid, uuid);
        }
    }

```

Figure 32 – Functions to convert uploaded csv to dspace format. The functions can process either data uploaded locally from the users to the eureka system or remote data that are downloaded with the provided url

```

    private void registerToDspace(KnowledgeObject knowledgeObject, String
        folderName, String metaDataUuid)
        throws IOException, NoSuchMethodException,
        IllegalAccessException, InvocationTargetException {
        //If filename is null there is no binary. Register anyway.
        if(knowledgeObject.getFilePath() == null &&
            knowledgeObject.getFileName() != null){
            return;
        }
        if(knowledgeObject.getFilePath() != null){
            addChecksum(knowledgeObject);
            addFilesize(knowledgeObject);
        }
        knowledgeObject = transformationService.normalize(knowledgeObject);
        Path metadataFolderPath =
            createFolderPath(dspaceConfig.getMetadataFolder(), metaDataUuid);
        createMetaData(knowledgeObject, metadataFolderPath, folderName);
    }

    private void addChecksum(KnowledgeObject knowledgeObject) {
        try (InputStream is =
            Files.newInputStream(Paths.get(knowledgeObject.getFilePath().toString()))) {
            String checksum =
                org.apache.commons.codec.digest.DigestUtils.md5Hex(is);
            knowledgeObject.getOptionalMetaData().put("knowledgeobject.checksum",
                checksum);
        } catch (IOException e) {
            log.error("Unable to generate checksum for file: {}",
                knowledgeObject.getFilePath(), e);
        }
    }

    private void addFilesize(KnowledgeObject knowledgeObject) {
        long filesize =
            FileUtils.sizeOf(knowledgeObject.getFilePath().toFile());
    }

```

```
knowledgeObject.getOptionalMetadata().put("creativework.filesize",  
String.valueOf(filesize));  
}
```

Figure 33 – Functions to automatically add metadata for the knowledge objects that are necessary for uploading into dspace.

